

Espacenet

Result list

201 results found for CPC=A61C5 AND ("root canal" OR endodontic)

Results 1 to 201 displayed

Filters:

Earliest priority date:

2012-01-01 To 2014-12-31

Query language: en / de / fr

Sort by: Priority date

1. SYSTEM AND METHOD FOR INTRODUCING PHOTSENSITIVE DYES VIA AN INSERT INTO A ROOT CANAL IN A TOOTH, METHOD FOR PRODUCING SAID DYE IMPREGNATED INSERT AND METHOD OF USING SAID DYE-IMPREGNATED INSERT

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
SYSTEM AND METHOD FOR INTRODUCING PHOTSENSITIVE DYES VIA AN INSERT INTO A ROOT CANAL IN A TOOTH, METHOD FOR PRODUCING SAID DYE IMPREGNATED INSERT AND METHOD OF USING SAID DYE-IMPREGNATED INSERT	TITLEBAUM RICHARD [US] TYAGI SOM [US]	TITLEBAUM RICHARD [US] TYAGI SOM [US]	US10136963B2 US2018000559A1	2014-12-22	A61C19/06 A61C5/50 A61K6/00 A61N5/06	A61C19/06 (EP,US) A61C5/40 (EP,US) A61C5/50 (US) A61K6/52 (EP,US) A61N5/062 (EP,US) A61C2201/002 (US) A61N2005/0606 (EP,US)	2018-01-04 2018-11-27	2016-06-30	056151468

2. DENTAL IRRIGATION, CLEANING AND DEBRIDEMENT SYSTEM, DEVICE AND INSTRUMENT

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
DENTAL IRRIGATION, CLEANING AND DEBRIDEMENT SYSTEM, DEVICE AND INSTRUMENT	YARED GHASSAN [CA] DE-DEUS GUSTAVO [BR]	YARED GHASSAN [CA] DE-DEUS GUSTAVO [BR] DE DEUS GUSTAVO [BR]	US10123851B2 US2017258552A1	2014-11-25	A61C17/02 A61C17/30 A61C5/40 A61C5/50	A61C17/0208 (EP,US) A61C17/028 (EP,US) A61C17/30 (US) A61C5/40 (EP,US) A61C5/50 (US)	2017-09-14 2018-11-13	2015-06-03	053365512

3. Methods and Devices for Treating Root Canals of Teeth

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
Methods and Devices for Treating Root Canals of Teeth	CLARK DAVID J [US] HENDERSON JEREMY [US]	CLARK DAVID J [US] HENDERSON JEREMY [US]	US2016143705A1	2014-11-21	A61C3/025 A61C5/02	A61C3/025 (EP,US) A61C5/40 (EP,US) A61C5/42 (EP,US)	2016-05-26	2016-05-26	056009073

4. HEATING CHARGER FOR DENTAL MATERIAL BY THERMOELECTRIC MODULE

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
HEATING CHARGER FOR DENTAL MATERIAL BY THERMOELECTRIC MODULE	JUNG DU ROK [KR] SHIN KYOUNG SOO [KR]	DXM CO LTD [KR]	KR101652763B1 KR20160056668A	2014-11-12	A61C5/04 A61C5/06	A61C5/55 (KR)	2016-05-20 2016-09-01	2016-05-20	056103794

5. DENTAL MATERIAL HEATING INFUSER FOR HEATING DENTAL MATERIAL BY PELTIER ELEMENT

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
DENTAL MATERIAL HEATING INFUSER FOR HEATING DENTAL MATERIAL BY PELTIER ELEMENT	JUNG DU ROK [KR] SHIN KYOUNG SOO [KR]	DXM CO LTD [KR]	US2017128158A1	2014-11-12	A61C5/55 A61C5/62 A61C5/66 H10N10/13	A61C5/55 (EP,US) A61C5/62 (EP,US) A61C5/66 (EP,US)	2017-05-11	2016-05-19	055954653

6. ANGLE PIECE HEAD

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
ANGLE PIECE HEAD	LEVY GUY-CHARLES [FR]	MICRO MEGA INTERNATIONAL MFT [FR]	US10383702B2 US2017348068A1	2014-11-07	A61C1/07 A61C1/12 A61C1/14 A61C5/42 F16H25/18	A61C1/07 (EP,KR,US) A61C1/12 (EP,KR,US) A61C1/148 (EP,KR,US) A61C5/42 (EP,KR,US) F16H25/186 (US)	2017-12-07 2019-08-20	2016-05-12	052684348

7. MOUTH GUARD

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
MOUTH GUARD	ELHEDI OUSSAMA [TN]	ELHEDI OUSSAMA [TN]	CA2970587A1	2014-10-31	A61B1/247 A61C5/82 A61C5/90	A61B1/247 (EP) A61C5/90 (EP)	2016-05-06	2016-03-30	055857954

8. DENTAL TREATMENT DEVICE WITH IMPROVED HEAD PART STRUCTURE

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
DENTAL TREATMENT DEVICE WITH IMPROVED HEAD PART STRUCTURE	HONG SUNG BIN [KR]	ORBITN CO LTD [KR]	WO2016060392A1	2014-10-14	A61C1/08 A61C5/02	A61C1/08 (EP) A61C5/40 (EP)	2016-04-21	2015-03-19	053027979

9. LENGTH MEASURING AND SETTING DEVICE OF ROOT CANAL ON THE DENTAL PILE

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
LENGTH MEASURING AND SETTING DEVICE OF ROOT CANAL ON THE DENTAL PILE	HA SANG YUN [KR]	HA SANG YUN [KR]	KR101924314B1 KR20160040917A	2014-10-06	A61C5/02 A61C19/04	A61C19/041 (EP,KR) A61C5/42 (KR) A61C5/44 (KR) A61C5/46 (KR)	2016-04-15 2018-12-03	2016-04-15	055801747

10. APPARATUS FOR DENTAL TREATMENT PROVIDED WITH UNIVERSAL DENTAL-RULER

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
APPARATUS FOR DENTAL TREATMENT PROVIDED WITH UNIVERSAL DENTAL-RULER	HONG SUNG BIN [KR]	HONG SUNG BIN [KR]	KR101512797B1	2014-10-06	A61C1/08 A61C19/04 A61C3/02 A61C5/02	A61C1/08 (KR) A61C19/04 (KR) A61C5/42 (KR) A61C5/44 (KR) A61C5/46 (KR)	2015-04-20	2015-04-20	053053400

11. ENDODONTIC HANDPIECE WITH ROTATIONAL AND VERTICAL MOTION

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
ENDODONTIC HANDPIECE WITH ROTATIONAL AND VERTICAL MOTION	GHADAMI MATTHEW [US]	GHADAMI MATTHEW [US]	US2017245960A1	2014-09-30	A61C1/02 A61C1/14 A61C5/40 A61C5/42	A61C1/02 (EP,US) A61C1/141 (EP,US) A61C5/40 (EP,US) A61C5/42 (US) A61C1/07 (EP,US)	2017-08-31	2016-04-07	055631423

12. ENDODONTIC APICAL PLUG

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
ENDODONTIC APICAL PLUG	AL SHEHRI MOHAMMED [SA]	AL SHEHRI MOHAMMED [SA]	US10441384B2 US2017360530A1	2014-09-24	A61C5/50 A61C5/55	A61C5/50 (EP,US) A61C5/55 (EP,US)	2017-12-21 2019-10-15	2015-07-07	059205987

13. METHOD FOR FORMING AN ENDODONTIC INSTRUMENT OR DEVICE

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
METHOD FOR FORMING AN ENDODONTIC INSTRUMENT OR DEVICE	LUEBKE NEILL HAMILTON [US]	GOLD STANDARD INSTR LLC [US]	US11267040B2 US2020316672A1	2014-09-09	A61C5/40 A61C5/42 B21F45/00	A61C5/40 (EP,US) A61C5/42 (US) B21F45/008 (US) A61C2201/007 (EP) Y10T29/49567 (US)	2020-10-08 2022-03-08	2016-03-17	055459500

14. PHOTO-CHEMICALLY ACTIVATED MICRO-BUBBLE BASED ROOT CANAL DISINFECTION

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
PHOTO-CHEMICALLY ACTIVATED MICRO-BUBBLE BASED ROOT CANAL DISINFECTION	KISHEN ANIL [CA]	KISHEN ANIL [CA] SYACT LLP [US]	US2016067149A1 US9987200B2	2014-09-04	A61C5/04 A61K6/00 A61M37/00 A61N5/06 A61C5/50 A61N5/067	A61C5/50 (EP,KR,US) A61K41/0057 (KR) A61K6/20 (EP,US) A61K6/52 (EP,US) A61K6/62 (EP,US) A61M37/0092 (EP,KR,US) A61N5/0603 (EP,KR,US) A61N5/062 (EP,KR,US) A61N5/0624 (EP,KR,US) A61N5/067 (EP) A61P1/02 (EP) A61P31/02 (EP) A61N2005/0606 (EP,KR,US) A61N2005/0644 (EP,US) A61N2005/0651 (EP,US) A61N2005/0654 (EP,KR,US) A61N5/067 (US)	2016-03-10 2018-06-05	2016-03-10	055436462

15. Customized Root Canal Obturation Cores and Methods of Making Customized Root Canal Obturation Cores

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
Customized Root Canal Obturation Cores and Methods of Making Customized Root Canal Obturation Cores	LEVIN MARTIN DAVID [US]	LEVIN MARTIN DAVID [US]	US2016045282A1 US9668824B2	2014-08-15	A61C5/04 A61B5/055 A61B6/51 A61C13/00 A61C9/00 B29C67/00 G05B19/4097 A61C5/50 B33Y10/00 B33Y50/02 B33Y80/00	A61B5/055 (KR) A61B6/032 (KR) A61B6/51 (KR,US) A61C13/0004 (EP,KR,US) A61C13/0013 (EP,KR,US) A61C13/0018 (EP,KR,US) A61C13/0019 (EP,KR,US) A61C5/50 (EP,KR,US) A61C5/66 (KR) A61C9/0053 (KR,US) B29C64/386 (KR) G05B19/4097	2016-02-18 2017-06-06	2016-02-18	053969442

						(KR,US) B33Y10/00 (US) B33Y50/02 (US) B33Y80/00 (US)			
16. CUSTOMIZED ROOT CANAL OBTURATION CORES AND METHODS OF MAKING CUSTOMIZED ROOT CANAL OBTURATION CORES									
Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
CUSTOMIZED ROOT CANAL OBTURATION CORES AND METHODS OF MAKING CUSTOMIZED ROOT CANAL OBTURATION CORES	LEVIN MARTIN DAVID [US]	LEVIN MARTIN DAVID [US]	US10426573B2 US2017245961A1	2014-08-15	A61C5/50 A61C13/00 B29C64/386 G05B19/4097 A61B5/055 A61B5/107 B33Y10/00 B33Y50/02 B33Y80/00	A61C13/0004 (EP,US) A61C13/0013 (EP,US) A61C13/0018 (EP,US) A61C13/0019 (EP,US) A61C5/50 (EP,US) B29C64/386 (EP,US) G05B19/4097 (US) A61B2576/02 (EP,US) A61B5/055 (EP) A61B5/1072 (EP,US) A61C2201/002 (EP,US) A61C2201/005 (EP,US) B33Y10/00 (EP,US) B33Y50/02 (EP,US) B33Y80/00 (EP,US) G16H30/40 (EP)	2017-08-31 2019-10-01	2017-08-31	059678759
17. DENTAL ALL-CERAMIC RESTORATION AND MANUFACTURING METHOD THEREOF									
Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
DENTAL ALL-CERAMIC RESTORATION AND MANUFACTURING METHOD THEREOF	SHEN JAMES ZHIJIAN [CN] ZHAO JING [CN]	HANGZHOU ERRAN TECHNOLOGY CO LTD [CN]	WO2016023470A1	2014-08-12	A61C13/083	A61C13/0004 (US) A61C13/0006 (US) A61C13/0022 (US) A61C13/0028 (US) A61C13/081 (US) A61C13/083 (EP,US) A61C13/26 (US) A61C13/30 (US) A61C13/34 (US) A61C5/20 (US) A61C5/35 (US) A61C5/77 (US) A61C8/0012 (US) A61C8/0048 (US) A61K6/802 (EP,US) A61K6/818 (EP,US)	2016-02-18	2016-02-18	055303877
18. TOOTH ENDODONTIC TREATMENT INSTRUMENT HAVING ENDODONTIC INSERTION DEPTH SENSING FUNCTION									

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
TOOTH ENDODONTIC TREATMENT INSTRUMENT HAVING ENDODONTIC INSERTION DEPTH SENSING FUNCTION	HONG SUNG BIN [KR]	ORBITN CO LTD [KR]	WO2016024722A1	2014-08-11	A61C19/04 A61C5/02	A61C19/04 (EP) A61C5/40 (EP)	2016-02-18	2014-12-12	052678133

19. HIGH FATIGUE RESISTANT WIRE

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
HIGH FATIGUE RESISTANT WIRE	ASLANIDIS DIMITRIOS [BE] SCHILDERMANS INGE [BE]	BEKAERT SA NV [BE]	US2017135784A1	2014-07-24	A61C5/42 B21C1/00 B21C1/02 C22C14/00 C22C19/00 C22C19/03 C22F1/10 C22F1/18	A61C5/42 (EP,US) B21C1/003 (US) B21C1/02 (US) C21D8/06 (EP,US) C22C14/00 (EP,US) C22C19/007 (EP,US) C22C19/03 (EP,US) C22F1/10 (EP,US) C22F1/183 (EP,US) A61C2201/007 (US)	2017-05-18	2016-01-28	051220471

20. APPARATUS FOR CLEANING ROOT CANAL OF TOOTH

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
APPARATUS FOR CLEANING ROOT CANAL OF TOOTH	LEE IN WHAN [KR] SUNG GIL HWAN [KR] BAEK SEUNG KI [KR] SUNG JAE YONG [KR]	B&L BIOTECH INC [KR]	KR101563430B1	2014-07-14	A61C17/02 A61C17/022 A61C5/02	A61C1/07 (KR) A61C17/0202 (KR) A61C5/40 (KR) A61G15/16 (KR)	2015-10-26	2015-10-26	054428304

21. MULTIPLE MEMORY MATERIALS AND SYSTEMS, METHODS AND APPLICATIONS THEREFOR

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
MULTIPLE MEMORY MATERIALS AND SYSTEMS, METHODS AND APPLICATIONS THEREFOR	KHAN MOHAMMAD IBRAHEM [CA] PEQUEGNAT ANDREW NIKOLAS [CA]	SMARTER ALLOYS INC [CA]	US11000741B2 US2017165532A1	2014-07-14	A61C5/42 A61C7/20 A61F2/82 A61L31/02 A61L31/14 A63B53/04 B23K26/00 B23K26/12 B23K26/354 G02C5/00 G02C5/14 G02C5/16 B22F3/105 B22F3/24 B23K26/0622 B23K26/08 B23K26/14 B32B15/00 B32B15/14 B32B27/12 B32B27/36 B32B27/40 B33Y10/00	A61C5/42 (EP,US) A61C7/20 (EP,US) A61F2/82 (US) A61L31/022 (EP,US) A61L31/14 (EP,US) A63B53/04 (EP,US) A61L31/14 (EP,US) A63B53/04 (EP,US) B22F10/00 (US) B22F10/28 (EP,US) B22F10/32 (EP,US) B22F12/226 (EP,US) B22F3/24 (EP,US) B23K26/0006 (EP,US) B23K26/0622	2017-06-15 2021-05-11	2016-01-21	055077761

B33Y30/00	(EP,US)
B33Y40/00	B23K26/08
C22F1/00	(EP,US)
B23K103/14	B23K26/0823
B29C71/04	(EP,US)
	B23K26/12 (US)
	B23K26/123
	(EP,US)
	B23K26/14
	(EP,US)
	B23K26/354
	(EP,US)
	B32B15/00
	(EP,US)
	B32B15/14
	(EP,US)
	B32B27/12
	(EP,US)
	B32B27/36
	(EP,US)
	B32B27/40
	(EP,US)
	B33Y10/00
	(EP,US)
	B33Y30/00
	(EP,US)
	C22F1/006
	(EP,US)
	G02C5/008 (US)
	G02C5/143 (US)
	G02C5/16
	(EP,US)
	A61C2201/007
	(EP,US)
	A61F2210/0014
	(EP,US)
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	A63B2209/00
	(EP,US)
	B22F12/41
	(EP,US)
	B22F12/43
	(EP,US)
	B22F12/63
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	B22F2998/00
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	(EP,US)
	B32B2250/02
	(EP,US)
	B32B2307/20
	(EP,US)
	B32B2307/51
	(EP,US)
	B32B2307/714
	(EP,US)

						B32B2437/00 (EP,US) B32B2535/00 (EP,US) Y02P10/25 (EP,US) B22F2998/00, B22F2003/247, B22F2003/248, B22F2003/241, ADD (EP,US)			
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22. COMPOSITIONS AND DELIVERY METHODS FOR TREATING DENTAL INFECTIONS, INFLAMMATION, SENSITIVITY, AND FOR USE IN DENTAL RESTORATIONS

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
COMPOSITIONS AND DELIVERY METHODS FOR TREATING DENTAL INFECTIONS, INFLAMMATION, SENSITIVITY, AND FOR USE IN DENTAL RESTORATIONS	MASRI RADJ [US]	UNIV MARYLAND [US]	US2021252263A1	2014-07-08	A61C19/06	A61C19/06	2021-08-19	2016-01-14	055065085
	DEPIREUX DIDIER [US]				A61C19/08	(EP,US)			
					A61C5/50	A61C19/063			
					A61K31/155	(EP,US)			
					A61K41/00	A61C19/08			
					A61K47/69	(EP,US)			
					A61K9/00	A61C5/50			
					A61K9/50	(EP,US)			
					A61M19/00	A61K31/155			
					A61M37/00	(EP,US)			
					A61N2/00	A61K41/00			
					A61N2/02	(EP,US)			
					A61N2/06	A61K47/6923			
						(EP,US)			
						A61K47/6929			
						(EP,US)			

23. ENDODONTIC INSTRUMENT FOR DRILLING ROOT CANALS

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
ENDODONTIC INSTRUMENT FOR DRILLING ROOT CANALS	BREGUET OLIVIER [CH]	FKG DENTAIRE SA [CH]	US2018177568A1	2014-07-07	A61C1/00	A61C1/0069	2018-06-28	2016-01-14	052338764
	ROUILLER JEAN-CLAUDE [CH]				A61C3/03	(IL,US)			
					A61C5/00	A61C17/20			
					A61C5/42	(EP,CN,IL,RU,US)			
						A61C5/00 (IL,RU)			
						A61C5/42			
						(EP,IL,KR,US)			
						A61C5/46 (KR)			
						C22F1/006 (IL)			
						A61C2201/007			

24. NICKEL-TITANIUM ENDODONTIC ROTARY FILE WITH HYBRID CROSS-SECTION

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
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NICKEL-TITANIUM ENDODONTIC ROTARY FILE WITH HYBRID CROSS-SECTION	KIM HYEON CHEOL [KR] LEE CHAN JOO [KR]	PUSAN NAT UNIV IND COOP FOUND [KR] KOREA IND TECH INST [KR]	KR101569202B1	2014-07-02	A61C5/02	A61C5/42 (KR) A61C5/46 (KR)	2015-11-13	2015-11-13	054610355
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25. HANDPIECE FOR NERVE TREATMENT CAPABLE OF SELECTING FILE ROTATION MODE

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
HANDPIECE FOR NERVE TREATMENT CAPABLE OF SELECTING FILE ROTATION MODE	SHIN JUNGPII [KR]	SAEYANG MICROTECH CO LTD [KR]	WO2015199274A1	2014-06-24	A61C1/06 A61C1/08 A61C5/02 A61C5/40	A61C1/02 (KR) A61C1/06 (EP,KR) A61C1/08 (EP,KR) A61C5/40 (EP)	2015-12-30	2015-12-30	054938345

26. Dental Device

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
Dental Device	KRASTEV PAVEL [US]	KRASTEV PAVEL [US]	US2015366633A1 US9326828B2	2014-06-19	A61C3/04 A61C5/04	A61C19/00 (EP,US) A61C3/04 (EP,US) A61C5/50 (EP,US)	2015-12-24 2016-05-03	2015-12-24	054868600

27. Endodontic therapy system, apparatus and method making use of a disposable CT registration tray device with pre-set radiographic registration markers

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
Endodontic therapy system, apparatus and method making use of a disposable CT registration tray device with pre-set radiographic registration markers	BUCHANAN L STEPHEN [US]	BUCHANAN L STEPHEN [US]	US9750582B1	2014-06-09	A61B6/03 A61B6/04 A61B6/51 A61C9/00	A61B90/39 (EP,US) A61C1/082 (EP,US) A61C5/40 (EP,US) A61C9/0006 (US) A61C9/004 (EP,US) A61B2090/3966 (EP,US) A61B6/032 (EP,US) A61B6/0492 (EP,US) A61B6/51 (EP,US) A61C1/084 (EP,US) A61C19/05 (EP,US)	2017-09-05	2017-09-05	059702161

28. TENON DENTAIRE EN MATERIAU COMPOSITE A BASE DE POLYMERE THERMOPLASTIQUE

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
TENON DENTAIRE EN MATERIAU COMPOSITE A BASE DE POLYMERE THERMOPLASTIQUE	REYNAUD PIERRE-LUC [FR] CHU MANH- QYUNH [FR]	RECH S TECH DENTAIRES RTD SOC D [FR] SOC DE RECHERCHES TECHNIQUES DENTAIRES RTD [FR]	FR3021521A1 FR3021521B1	2014-05-30	A61C13/30 A61K6/884	A61C5/50 (EP) A61K6/884 (EP) A61K6/54, C08L71/12, INV (EP) A61K6/54, C08L75/00, INV (EP)	2015-12-04 2021-04-23	2015-12-04	051225786

29. ROOT CANAL TREATING DEVICE

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
ROOT CANAL TREATING DEVICE	NAKAI TERUJI [JP]	J MORITA MFG CORP [JP]	US10251736B2 US2017071713A1	2014-05-28	A61B1/04 A61B1/247 A61B5/00	A61B1/044 (US) A61B1/247 (US) A61B34/20 (EP)	2017-03-16 2019-04-09	2015-09-24	054200694

					A61B6/03	A61B5/0084 (US)		
					A61B6/51	A61B5/0088 (US)		
					A61C1/08	A61B6/03 (US)		
					A61C19/04	A61B6/032 (US)		
					A61C19/00	A61B6/463		
					A61C5/40	(EP,US)		
					A61C5/42	A61B6/51		
					A61C5/44	(EP,US)		
					A61B34/20	A61B6/5247		
						(EP,US)		
						A61B6/5294 (EP)		
						A61B6/547 (EP)		
						A61C1/0015 (EP)		
						A61C1/082 (US)		
						A61C1/186 (EP)		
						A61C19/04 (US)		
						A61C19/041 (US)		
						A61C19/042		
						(EP,US)		
						A61C5/40		
						(EP,US)		
						A61C5/42 (US)		
						A61C5/44 (US)		
						A61B2034/2048		
						(EP)		
						A61B2034/2051		
						(EP)		
						A61B2034/2055		
						(EP,US)		
						A61B2034/2065		
						(US)		
						A61B2090/3983		
						(EP) A61B34/25		
						(EP) A61B90/361		
						(EP) A61C9/0053		
						(EP)		

30. ROOT CANAL TREATING DISPLAY DEVICE, ROOT CANAL TREATING UNIT, AND DENTAL IMAGE DISPLAY METHOD

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
ROOT CANAL TREATING DISPLAY DEVICE, ROOT CANAL TREATING UNIT, AND DENTAL IMAGE DISPLAY METHOD	NAKAI TERUJI [JP]	J MORITA MFG CORP [JP]	US11135013B2 US2017065370A1	2014-05-21	A61B34/10 A61B6/03 A61B6/51 A61C1/00 A61C19/04 A61C3/02 A61B5/00 A61B5/055 A61C5/42 A61C9/00 A61B90/00	A61B34/10 (EP,US) A61B5/0036 (EP,US) A61B5/0059 (EP,US) A61B5/0066 (EP,US) A61B5/0088 (EP,US) A61B5/055 (EP) A61B5/4542 (EP,US) A61B5/682 (EP,US) A61B6/03 (EP,US) A61B6/463 (EP,US) A61B6/466 (EP,US) A61B6/51 (EP,US)	2017-03-09 2021-10-05	2015-10-07	054346160

						A61B6/5247 (EP,US) A61C1/0015 (US) A61C19/041 (US) A61C3/02 (US) A61C5/42 (EP,US) A61C9/0053 (EP,US) A61B2034/107 (EP,US) A61B2090/376 (EP,US) A61B5/4836 (EP) G06T2207/10081 (EP,US) G06T2207/30036 (EP,US)		
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31. DENTAL GEL COMPOSITION OF PAPAIN FOR THE ATRAUMATIC TREATMENT OF CARIES AND METHOD OF PREPARING SAME

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
DENTAL GEL COMPOSITION OF PAPAIN FOR THE ATRAUMATIC TREATMENT OF CARIES AND METHOD OF PREPARING SAME	DOBBOLETTA MAURICIO [AR]	BRIX USA LLC [US]	US10137178B2 US2017100464A1	2014-05-20	A61C19/06 A61K38/48 A61K47/02 A61K47/10 A61K47/14 A61K47/18 A61K47/22 A61K47/26 A61K47/36 A61K9/06 A61C5/62 A61K8/04 A61K8/11 A61K8/24 A61K8/34 A61K8/37 A61K8/41 A61K8/49 A61K8/66 A61K8/86 A61Q11/00	A61C19/063 (US) A61C5/62 (EP,US) A61K38/4873 (EP,US) A61K47/02 (US) A61K47/10 (US) A61K47/14 (US) A61K47/18 (US) A61K47/22 (US) A61K47/26 (US) A61K47/36 (US) A61K47/22 (US) A61K47/36 (US) A61K8/042 (EP,US) A61K8/11 (EP,BR,US) A61K8/19 (BR) A61K8/24 (EP,US) A61K8/345 (EP,BR,US) A61K8/37 (EP,US) A61K8/41 (EP,BR,US) A61K8/49 (EP,US) A61K8/66 (EP,US) A61K8/73 (BR) A61K8/86 (EP,US) A61K8/97 (BR) A61K9/06 (US) A61P1/02 (EP) A61P31/00 (EP) A61Q11/00 (EP,BR,US) C12Y304/22002 (EP,US) A61K2800/91 (EP,US)	2017-04-13 2018-11-27	2015-11-19	054554663

32. INSTRUMENT POUR LE NETTOYAGE ET FACULTATIVEMENT LA PROTECTION D'UNE ZONE A TRAITER ET DISPOSITIF LE COMPRENANT

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
INSTRUMENT POUR LE NETTOYAGE ET FACULTATIVEMENT LA PROTECTION D'UNE ZONE A TRAITER ET DISPOSITIF LE COMPRENANT	ROLIN FRANCOIS [FR]	ROLIN FRANCOIS [FR]	FR3020567A1 FR3020567B1	2014-04-30	A61C5/02 A61C5/04 A61B17/00 A61C17/00	A61C17/0202 (EP) A61C17/0208 (EP) A61C19/004 (EP) A61C5/50 (EP) A61C5/62 (EP) A61C9/0026 (EP)	2015-11-06 2017-04-28	2015-11-05	051063692

33. ENDODONTIC TREATMENT WITH LONG TERM DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
ENDODONTIC TREATMENT WITH LONG TERM DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM	AMMON DAN [US] WILKINSON KEVIN [US] GUTMANN JAMES L [US]	DENTSPLY INT INC [US]	EP3137011A1 EP3137011A4	2014-04-29	A61C5/40 A61C5/48 A61K6/00	A61C5/40 (EP) A61K6/54 (EP) A61K6/69 (EP) A61P1/02 (EP) A61P29/00 (EP) A61P31/04 (EP)	2017-03-08 2018-01-03	2015-11-05	054359294

34. Wurzelkanalstift sowie Verfahren zu dessen Herstellung

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
Wurzelkanalstift sowie Verfahren zu dessen Herstellung	TOSKAS GEORGIOS [GR] CHERIF CHOKRI [DE] HANNIG CHRISTIAN [DE] HUND ROLF- DIETER [DE] CHENG TONG [DE] GRYCHTOL SUSANN [DE] BARTUSCH MATTHIAS [DE]	UNIV DRESDEN TECH [DE]	DE102014105793B3	2014-04-24	A61C5/02 A61C5/50	A61C5/50 (EP)	2015-06-03	2015-06-03	053058691

35. REINFORCEMENT STRUCTURE FOR CORONAL-RADICULAR DENTAL RECONSTITUTION, METHOD FOR PERFORMING CORONAL-RADICULAR DENTAL RECONSTITUTION, CORONAL-RADICULAR DENTAL RECONSTITUTION

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
REINFORCEMENT STRUCTURE FOR CORONAL-RADICULAR DENTAL RECONSTITUTION, METHOD FOR PERFORMING CORONAL-RADICULAR DENTAL RECONSTITUTION, CORONAL-RADICULAR DENTAL RECONSTITUTION	MANEUF BERNARD [FR] COLLOMBIN ANDRÉ [FR] CLUNET-COSTE BRUNO [FR]	MANEUF BERNARD [FR] COLLOMBIN ANDRÉ [FR] CLUNET-COSTE BRUNO [FR]	US2015305829A1 US9839493B2	2014-04-23	A61C5/00 A61C5/35 A61C13/30	A61C13/30 (EP,US) A61C5/35 (EP,US)	2015-10-29 2017-12-12	2015-10-23	051014358

36. DENTAL MATRIX AND DENTAL MATRIX SYSTEM

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
DENTAL MATRIX AND DENTAL MATRIX SYSTEM	CLARK DAVID J [US]	CLARK DAVID J [US]	US12042349B2 US2022039916A1	2014-03-25	A61C5/85	A61C5/85 (EP,US)	2022-02-10 2024-07-23	2015-10-01	054196357

37. DRILL LIMIT SYSTEM AND METHOD OF USING SAME

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
DRILL LIMIT SYSTEM AND METHOD OF USING SAME	ARAVENA INES [US]	IMPLANT DIRECT SYBRON INTERNAT LLC	US2015257852A1 US9713510B2	2014-03-17	A61C1/08 B23Q16/00 A61B90/00	A61C1/082 (US) A61C1/084 (EP,US) A61C5/44	2015-09-17 2017-07-25	2015-09-17	054067681

		[US] IMPLANT DIRECT SYBRON INT LLC [US]			A61C1/18 A61C8/00	(EP,US) A61B2090/033 (EP,US) A61C1/186 (EP,US) A61C8/0089 (EP) Y10T29/49826 (EP)			
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38. DRILL LIMIT SYSTEM AND METHOD OF USING SAME

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
DRILL LIMIT SYSTEM AND METHOD OF USING SAME	ARAVENA INES [US]	IMPLANT DIRECT SYBRON INT LLC [US]	US10213273B2 US2017319290A1	2014-03-17	A61C1/08 B23Q16/00 A61C5/44 A61B90/00 A61C1/18 A61C8/00	A61C1/082 (US) A61C1/084 (EP,US) A61C5/44 (EP,US) A61B2090/033 (EP) A61B2090/034 (EP,US) A61C1/186 (EP,US) A61C8/0089 (EP) Y10T29/49826 (EP)	2017-11-09 2019-02-26	2017-11-09	060242450

39. INDIRECT ATRAUMATIC METHOD FOR RESTORING TEETH DECAYED/FRACTURED BELOW THE GUM LINE

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
INDIRECT ATRAUMATIC METHOD FOR RESTORING TEETH DECAYED/FRACTURED BELOW THE GUM LINE	MELIKYAN MELIKSET LITVINOVICH [US] MELIKYAN KARINE MELIKSETOVNA [US] MELIKYAN GAREGIN MELIKSETOVNA [RU] MELIKYAN GAREGIN MELIKSETOVICH [RU]	MELIKYAN MELIKSET LITVINOVICH [US] MELIKYAN KARINE MELIKSETOVNA [US] MELIKSETOVNA [RU] MELIKYAN GAREGIN MELIKSETOVICH [RU]	US10610331B2 US2017007358A1	2014-03-13	A61C5/00 A61C5/35 A61C5/50 A61C5/70 A61C5/77 A61C13/30	A61C13/30 (EP,US) A61C5/35 (EP,US) A61C5/50 (EP,US) A61C5/70 (EP,US) A61C5/77 (EP,US)	2017-01-12 2020-04-07	2015-04-20	053289495

40. WIRE MESH COMPOSITE PROSTHESIS

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
WIRE MESH COMPOSITE PROSTHESIS	MELIKYAN MELIKSET LITVINOVICH [US] MELIKYAN KARINE MELIKSETOVNA [US] MELIKYAN GAREGIN MELIKSETOVICH [RU]	MELIKYAN MELIKSET LITVINOVICH [US] MELIKYAN KARINE MELIKSETOVNA [US] MELIKYAN GAREGIN MELIKSETOVICH [RU]	US2020229898A1	2014-03-13	A61C13/09 A61C5/35	A61C13/09 (US) A61C13/30 (EP) A61C5/35 (US) A61C5/73 (EP)	2020-07-23	2020-07-23	071609491

41. ROOT CANAL IRRIGATION NEEDLE ENHANCEMENT

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
ROOT CANAL IRRIGATION NEEDLE ENHANCEMENT	DETURMENY ARNAUD [FR]	DETURMENY ARNAUD [FR]	US2017071710A1	2014-03-11	A61C17/02	A61C17/02 (EP,US) A61C5/40 (EP,US) A61C5/50 (EP,US)	2017-03-16	2015-09-17	050549191

42. Zahnmedizinische Vorrichtung

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
Zahnmedizinische Vorrichtung	CSÖGÖR ANDRÁS [DE]	CSÖGÖR ANDRÁS [DE]	DE102014003398A1 DE102014003398B4	2014-03-10	A61C13/38 A61C19/00	A61C19/02 (EP) A61C5/50 (EP) A61C2202/00 (EP)	2015-09-10 2016-01-21	2015-09-10	053883768

43. ENDODONTIC FILE FOR ASSESSING ROOT CANAL DEPTH

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
ENDODONTIC FILE FOR ASSESSING ROOT CANAL DEPTH	ANDREOU PANAYIOTIS [CA]	ANDREOU PANAYIOTIS [CA]	US2015230902A1	2014-02-18	A61C19/04 A61C5/02	A61C19/041 (EP,US) A61C19/042 (EP,US) A61C5/42 (EP,US)	2015-08-20	2015-08-20	053797046

44. Dentalinstrument zum Auftragen von Dentalmassen

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
Dentalinstrument zum Auftragen von Dentalmassen	ESSLER MICHAEL [DE] HABIBI-NAINI SASAN [DE]	PHENEO GMBH [DE]	DE102014001502A1	2014-02-06	A61C5/04 A61C5/50	A61C3/005 (EP) A61C5/50 (EP)	2015-08-06	2015-08-06	053546841

45. Zahnmedizinische Vorrichtung

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
Zahnmedizinische Vorrichtung	CSÖGÖR ANDRÁS [DE]	CSÖGÖR ANDRÁS [DE]	DE102014001279A1 DE102014001279B4	2014-01-31	A61C5/02 A61C5/40	A61C19/041 (EP) A61C5/40 (EP)	2015-08-06 2016-12-29	2015-08-06	053546792

46. Füllvorrichtung und Verfahren zum Füllen eines Wurzelkanals

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
Füllvorrichtung und Verfahren zum Füllen eines Wurzelkanals	OEHME BERND [DE] BRAUN [DE] ANDREAS [DE]	SIRONA DENTAL SYSTEMS GMBH [DE]	DE102014201786A1	2014-01-31	A61C13/15 A61C5/02 A61C5/40 A61C5/55	A61C5/40 (EP) A61C5/55 (EP)	2015-08-06	2015-08-06	053546983

47. APPARATUS FOR CHARGING ROOT CANAL USING INDUCTION TYPE

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
APPARATUS FOR CHARGING ROOT CANAL USING INDUCTION TYPE	LEE IN WHAN [KR] SUNG GIL HWAN [KR] PARK JUNG HWAN [KR] BAEK SEUNG KI [KR]	B & L BIOTECH INC [KR]	KR101472704B1	2014-01-13	A61C5/02 A61C5/04	A61C3/08 (KR) A61C5/55 (KR) A61C5/62 (KR) A61C2204/002 (KR)	2014-12-15	2014-12-15	052678857

48. Verfahren zum Herstellen einer Spülkanüle, Spülkanüle und Spüleinrichtung.

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
Verfahren zum Herstellen einer Spülkanüle, Spülkanüle und Spüleinrichtung.	JOACHIM FRITZE [DE]	TRANSCODENT GMBH & CO KG [DE]	CH710746B1	2014-01-09	A61C17/02 A61C5/40	A61C17/02 (EP,CH,US) A61C5/40 (EP)	2018-05-15	2015-07-16	049917587

49. A DENTAL RESTORATIVE DEVICE AND METHOD OF USING THE SAME

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
A DENTAL RESTORATIVE DEVICE AND METHOD OF USING THE SAME	MCDONALD SIMON P [NZ] AUBONE ALEJANDRO [NZ]	RHONIUM IP LTD [NZ]	US10080629B2 US201632460A1	2014-01-09	A61C13/15 A61C19/04 A61C5/12 A61C13/083 A61C13/087 A61C13/09 A61C13/107 A61C19/02 A61C5/73 A61C5/77 A61K6/02 A61K6/884	A61C13/001 (EP,US) A61C13/0022 (EP,US) A61C13/083 (EP,US) A61C13/087 (EP,US) A61C13/087 (EP,US) A61C13/09 (EP,US) A61C13/09 (EP,US) A61C19/02 (EP,US) A61C13/09 (EP,US) A61C19/02 (EP,US)	2016-11-10 2018-09-25	2015-07-16	053524467

					A61C13/00 A61C5/88 A61C13/15 A61C19/04	A61C5/73 (EP,US) A61C5/77 (EP,US) A61C5/88 (EP,US) A61K6/802 (EP,US) A61C19/003 (EP,US) A61C19/04 (EP,US) A61C2202/01 (EP,US)			
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50. PIEZOELECTRIC DEVICE AND CIRCUITRY

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
PIEZOELECTRIC DEVICE AND CIRCUITRY	POND GARY J [US] BAETEN JOHN [US] ALLEN MICHAEL W [US]	INTER MED INC [US]	US11648083B2 US2019357996A1	2013-12-27	A61C1/00 A61C1/07 A61C17/02 A61N7/00 B06B1/02 H10N30/20 H10N30/80 A61C5/40 A61C5/50	A61C1/0015 (EP,US) A61C1/07 (EP,US) A61C17/0202 (EP,US) A61N7/00 (US) B06B1/0207 (EP,US) H10N30/20 (US) H10N30/802 (US) A61C5/40 (EP,US) A61C5/50 (EP,US)	2019-11-28 2023-05-16	2015-07-02	052464552

51. VIBRATING MEDICAL DEVICE FOR MINIMALLY INVASIVE PROCEDURES

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
VIBRATING MEDICAL DEVICE FOR MINIMALLY INVASIVE PROCEDURES	CHEVALIER ERIC [CH]	CHEVALIER ERIC [CH]	WO2015097251A2 WO2015097251A3	2013-12-23	A61B17/22 A61C5/42 A61B18/26 A61C5/02	A61B17/22012 (EP,US) A61B18/26 (EP) A61C1/07 (EP) A61C19/041 (EP) A61C5/42 (EP) A61C5/44 (EP) A61B2017/22027 (EP) A61B2018/00345 (EP) A61B2018/00505 (EP) A61B2018/00511 (EP) A61B2018/00535 (EP) A61B2018/00577 (EP) A61B2018/00642 (EP) A61B2018/00702 (EP) A61B2018/00863 (EP) A61B2018/0088 (EP) A61B2018/00982	2015-07-02 2015-08-13	2015-07-02	052273161

						(EP) A61B2090/064 (EP) A61B2090/065 (EP) A61B2090/3735 (EP) A61B2218/002 (EP) A61M2205/0238 (EP) A61M2205/33 (EP) A61M2205/3303 (EP) A61M2205/35 (EP) A61M2205/3507 (EP)			
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52. USE OF A MEASURING DEVICE FOR DENTAL CAVITIES

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
USE OF A MEASURING DEVICE FOR DENTAL CAVITIES	FRITZE JOACHIM [DE] WITTEN MELANIE [DE]	TRANSCODENT GMBH & CO KG [DE]	WO201508660A1	2013-12-11	A61C19/04 A61C5/04 A61C5/62	A61C19/04 (EP) A61C5/62 (EP)	2015-06-18	2015-06-18	049753068

53. Multi-Directional Handpiece

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
Multi-Directional Handpiece	SHOTTON VINCENT [US] AMMON DAN [US] KARAZIVAN NAIM [CA]	DENTSPLY INT INC [US]	US2015164614A1 US9833299B2	2013-12-10	A61C5/02 A61C1/02 A61C1/12 A61C1/14 A61C1/18 A61C1/00 A61C1/07 A61C5/40 A61C5/42	A61C1/003 (EP,US) A61C1/02 (EP,US) A61C1/07 (EP,US) A61C1/12 (EP,US) A61C1/148 (EP,US) A61C1/185 (EP,US) A61C5/40 (EP,US) A61C5/42 (EP,US)	2015-06-18 2017-12-05	2015-06-18	052134462

54. ENDODONTIC FILE

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
ENDODONTIC FILE	SPRECHMAN KENNETH C [US]	SPRECHMAN KENNETH C [US]	US2016302883A1	2013-12-05	A61C5/02 A61C5/42	A61C5/42 (EP,US)	2016-10-20	2015-06-11	053274185

55. DENTAL MILL BLANK, PROCESS FOR PRODUCTION AND USE THEREOF

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
DENTAL MILL BLANK, PROCESS FOR PRODUCTION AND USE THEREOF	JAHNS MICHAEL SCHNAGL HANS R	3M INNOVATIVE PROPERTIES CO	CN105792773A CN105792773B	2013-12-04	A61C13/00 A61C5/77 C04B35/48 C04B41/45	A61C13/00 (RU) A61C13/0004 (EP,US) A61C13/0006 (US) A61C13/0022 (EP,US) A61C5/77 (US) A61C7/00 (US) A61C8/0012 (EP,US)	2016-07-20 2019-05-10	2015-06-11	049725019

A61C8/005 (EP,US)
C04B35/48 (RU)
C04B35/486 (EP,US)
C04B35/4885 (US)
C04B35/62605 (US)
C04B35/6261 (US)
C04B35/62645 (US) C04B35/632 (EP,US)
C04B35/634 (EP,US)
C04B35/64 (EP,US)
C04B41/45 (RU)
C04B2235/3217 (EP,US)
C04B2235/3224 (EP,US)
C04B2235/3225 (EP,US)
C04B2235/3239 (US)
C04B2235/3241 (US)
C04B2235/3244 (US)
C04B2235/3256 (US)
C04B2235/3262 (EP,US)
C04B2235/3267 (EP,US)
C04B2235/3272 (EP,US)
C04B2235/3281 (US)
C04B2235/3298 (EP,US)
C04B2235/449 (EP,US)
C04B2235/604 (EP,US)
C04B2235/612 (EP,US)
C04B2235/661 (EP,US)
C04B2235/72 (EP,US)
C04B2235/725 (EP,US)
C04B2235/765 (EP,US)
C04B2235/77 (EP,US)
C04B2235/781 (EP,US)
C04B2235/94

						(EP,US) C04B2235/945 (US) C04B2235/9615 (EP,US) C04B2235/9646 (EP,US) C04B2235/9661 (EP,US)			
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56. Instruments And Coatings Formed From A Porous Material

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
Instruments And Coatings Formed From A Porous Material	SHOTTON VINCENT [US] DAMIEN CHRISTOPHER [US] AMMON DAN [US]	DENTSPLY INT INC [US] DENTSPLY SIRONA INC [US]	US10182883B2 US2015366635A1	2013-11-20	A61C5/02 A61C5/42	A61C5/42 (EP,US) A61C2201/007 (EP,US) Y10T29/49567 (EP) Y10T29/49568 (US)	2015-12-24 2019-01-22	2015-07-23	052023670

57. METODO DI CONTROLLO DI UNO STRUMENTO ENDODONTICO PER CURE CANALARI

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
METODO DI CONTROLLO DI UNO STRUMENTO ENDODONTICO PER CURE CANALARI	POLI DANIELE	BY DENTAL S R L	ITRM20130638A1	2013-11-19	A61C5/40	A61C1/003 (EP) A61C1/186 (EP) A61C5/40 (EP)	2015-05-20	2015-05-20	049780236

58. TOOTH PROSTHESIS AS ADMINISTRATION FORM FOR TREATING CHRONIC DISEASES

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
TOOTH PROSTHESIS AS ADMINISTRATION FORM FOR TREATING CHRONIC DISEASES	RUPPERT KLAUS [DE]	HERAEUS KULZER GMBH [DE] KULZER & CO GMBH [DE]	EP3068450A1 EP3068450B1	2013-11-13	A61K6/00 A61K9/00 A61L27/54 A61M31/00 A61C19/06 A61C5/50 A61C8/00 A61K31/13 A61K31/44 A61K45/06 A61K6/69 (EP) A61K6/71 (EP) A61K9/0063 (EP) A61L27/54 (EP) A61P25/28 A61P3/10 A61P31/04	A61C19/063 (EP) A61C5/50 (EP) A61C8/00 (EP) A61C8/005 (EP) A61K31/137 (EP) A61K31/444 (EP) A61K38/28 (EP) A61K45/06 (EP) A61K6/69 (EP) A61K6/71 (EP) A61K9/0063 (EP) A61L27/54 (EP) A61P25/16 (EP) A61P25/24 (EP) A61P25/28 (EP) A61P3/10 (EP) A61P31/04 (EP) A61K47/02 (EP) A61K47/32 (EP) A61K6/30, C08L33/08, INV (EP) A61K6/30, C08L33/10, INV (EP) A61K6/40, C08L33/08, INV (EP) A61K6/40, C08L33/10, INV (EP)	2016-09-21 2019-02-27	2015-05-13	051932323

59. APPARATUS AND METHOD FOR ENDODONTIC TREATMENT

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
APPARATUS AND METHOD FOR	LIFSHITZ AMNON [IL]	FLUIDFILE LTD [IL]		2013-10-23	A61C5/02 A61C5/40	A61C17/0202 (EP,IL,KR)		2015-04-30	052992366

ENDODONTIC TREATMENT	DARSHAN YEHUDA [IL]		EP3060158A1 EP3060158A4		A61C17/02 A61C5/50	A61C17/0208 (EP,IL,KR) A61C17/0217 (EP,IL,KR) A61C17/028 (EP,IL,KR) A61C3/025 (EP,IL,KR) A61C5/40 (EP,IL)	2016-08-31 2017-09-13		
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60. DENTAL ABUTMENT AND DENTAL RESIN MATERIAL

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
DENTAL ABUTMENT AND DENTAL RESIN MATERIAL	ANDO HIROSHI [JP]	UNIX JAPAN CO LTD [JP]	WO2015059761A1	2013-10-22	A61C13/087 A61C13/093 A61C13/30 A61C5/08 A61C5/70 A61C5/77	A61C13/30 (EP,US) A61C5/70 (EP,US) A61C5/77 (EP,US)	2015-04-30	2015-04-30	052992401

61. METHOD OF MAKING A DENTAL PROSTHESIS

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
METHOD OF MAKING A DENTAL PROSTHESIS	JUNG DANIEL YONIL [US] JUNG YUNOH [US]	B & D DENTAL CORP [US]	US2015111172A1 US9168114B2	2013-10-17	A61C13/00 A61C13/225 A61C5/77 A61C13/271 A61C19/06 A61C13/09 A61C9/00	A61C13/0003 (KR,US) A61C13/0004 (EP,KR,US) A61C13/09 (KR) A61C13/225 (KR) A61C13/26 (EP,KR,US) A61C19/063 (EP,KR,US) A61C5/77 (EP,KR,US) A61C9/002 (KR) A61C13/09 (EP,US) A61C9/002 (EP,US) Y10T29/49567 (EP,US)	2015-04-23 2015-10-27	2015-04-23	052826480

62. RETRIEVABLE DETENT RETAINED DENTAL PROSTHESIS SYSTEM AND METHODS

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
RETRIEVABLE DETENT RETAINED DENTAL PROSTHESIS SYSTEM AND METHODS	CHESLER MILKA [IL]	CHESLER MILKA [IL]	US2015099238A1	2013-10-08	A61C13/225 A61C3/02 A61C5/08 A61C8/00	A61C13/30 (EP,US) A61C5/70 (EP,US) A61C8/0048 (EP,US) A61C8/005 (EP,US)	2015-04-09	2015-04-09	052777228

63. METHOD OF MANUFACTURING NI-TI FILE FOR ENDODONTICS TREATMENT

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
METHOD OF MANUFACTURING NI-TI FILE FOR ENDODONTICS TREATMENT	NOH HAK [KR] OH SEUNG [KR]	NCL KOREA CO LTD [KR]	KR101463802B1	2013-10-04	A61C5/02	A61C5/42 (KR) A61C5/46 (KR) B21F23/005 (KR) B21F45/008 (KR) B21F7/00 (KR) B24B3/605 (KR) B24B3/607 (KR) C25F3/16 (KR)	2014-11-24	2014-11-24	052291247

64. DENTAL TREATING APPARATUS AND DRIVING METHOD FOR THE SAME

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication	Earliest	IPC	CPC	Publication	Earliest	Family
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DENTAL TREATING APPARATUS AND DRIVING METHOD FOR THE SAME	KATSUDA NAOKI [JP] YAMASHITA SEIICHIRO [JP] UEDA TOMOAKI [JP] HIJIKATA HIDEO [JP]	MORITA MFG [JP] J MORITA MFG CORP [JP]	number US2015086937A1 US9895205B2	priority 2013-09-20	A61C5/02 A61C1/00 A61C1/02 A61C1/18 A61C19/04 A61C5/40 A61C5/42 A61C5/44 A61C5/48	A61C1/186 (EP,US) A61C19/041 (EP,US) A61C5/40 (EP,US) A61C5/42 (EP,US) A61C5/44 (EP,US) A61C5/44 (EP,US) A61C5/48 (EP,US) A61C5/48 (EP,US) A61C1/0023 (EP,US) A61C1/003 (EP,US)	date 2015-03-26 2018-02-20	publication 2015-03-25	number 051518504
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65. DENTAL TREATING APPARATUS

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
DENTAL TREATING APPARATUS	KATSUDA NAOKI [JP] YAMASHITA SEIICHIRO [JP] UEDA TOMOAKI [JP] HIJIKATA HIDEO [JP]	MORITA MFG [JP] J MORITA MFG CORP [JP]	US2015086941A1 US9681929B2	2013-09-20	A61C5/02 A61C1/00 A61C1/18 A61C19/04 A61C5/40 A61C5/44 A61C5/48	A61C1/186 (EP,US) A61C19/041 (EP,US) A61C5/40 (EP,US) A61C5/44 (EP,US) A61C5/44 (EP,US) A61C5/48 (EP,US) A61C1/0023 (EP,US) A61C1/003 (EP,US)	2015-03-26 2017-06-20	2015-03-25	051518503

66. ELECTRICAL DISCHARGE IRRIGATOR APPARATUS

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
ELECTRICAL DISCHARGE IRRIGATOR APPARATUS	FREGOSO GILBERT [US] HECKERMAN BRAD [US] AVNIEL YUVAL CHARLES [US] MEUCHEL DENNIS [US]	AMERICAN EAGLE INSTR INC [US] G&H TECH LLC [US]	EP3046504A1 EP3046504A4 EP3046504B1	2013-09-20	A61C5/02 A61C17/02 A61C19/06 A61C5/40 A61C5/50 A61N1/44	A61C17/02 (EP,US) A61C5/40 (EP) A61C5/50 (EP) A61N1/44 (EP)	2016-07-27 2017-06-14 2019-04-17	2015-03-26	052689461

67. Endodontic instrument having lowered risk of being broken

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
Endodontic instrument having lowered risk of being broken	HUR DUCK SU [KR] MO YONG SEOB [KR]	HUR DUCK SU [KR]	KR20150030862A	2013-09-13	A61C3/02 A61C5/02	A61C5/42 (KR) A61C5/46 (KR) A61C5/48 (KR)	2015-03-23	2015-03-23	053024688

68. ULTRASONIC RING TIP TO ACTIVATE ENDODONTIC INSTRUMENTS

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
ULTRASONIC RING TIP TO ACTIVATE ENDODONTIC INSTRUMENTS	WONG HERIBERTO BUJANDA [MX] PRECIADO HERIBERTO BUJANDA [MX]	WONG HERIBERTO BUJANDA [MX] PRECIADO HERIBERTO BUJANDA [MX]	US2015064647A1 US9839492B2	2013-09-05	A61C5/02 A61C1/07 A61C1/14 A61C5/42	A61C1/07 (EP,US) A61C1/148 (EP,US) A61C5/42 (EP,US)	2015-03-05 2017-12-12	2015-03-05	052583727

69. ENDODONTIC INSTRUMENT WITH ROUGH SURFACES AND METHOD FOR PRODUCING SUCH AN INSTRUMENT

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
ENDODONTIC INSTRUMENT WITH ROUGH SURFACES AND METHOD FOR PRODUCING SUCH AN INSTRUMENT	PERNOT JACQUES [FR] ROLLAND XAVIER [FR] EUWARD HUBERT [FR]	NEOLIX [FR]	US2016206401A1	2013-08-30	A61C5/02 A61C5/42 B23P15/32	A61C5/42 (EP,US) B23H7/02 (EP,US) B23H9/008 (EP,US) B23P15/32 (US)	2016-07-21	2015-03-05	049667359

70. TOOL FOR CLEANING PULP CANALS OF TEETH

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
TOOL FOR CLEANING PULP CANALS OF TEETH	KIM GUN TAE [KR]	SIWON CO LTD [KR]	KR101486202B1	2013-08-21	A61C17/02 A61C5/02	A61C1/07 (KR) A61C17/16 (KR) A61C5/40 (KR) A61C5/46 (KR)	2015-01-29	2015-01-29	052592851

71. SYSTEM AND METHOD FOR AUTOMATING MEDICAL PROCEDURES

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
SYSTEM AND METHOD FOR AUTOMATING MEDICAL PROCEDURES	AKEEL HADI [US] SHEHAB YAZ [US] WONG GEORGE [US]	BRACHIUM LABS LLC [US] BRACHIUM INC [US]	US2015057675A1 US9675419B2	2013-08-21	A61B19/00 G06F19/00 A61B34/30 A61B34/32 A61C1/00 A61C17/00 A61C5/40 A61C5/70 A61C7/00 A61C7/14 A61C8/00 A61B34/00 A61B34/10 A61B34/20 A61B90/00 A61C3/02 A61G15/14	A61B34/10 (EP,US) A61B34/30 (EP,US) A61B34/32 (EP,US) A61C1/00 (EP,US) A61C1/00 (US) A61C1/082 (EP,US) A61C17/00 (EP,US) A61C5/30 (US) A61C5/40 (EP,US) A61C5/70 (EP,US) A61C7/002 (EP,US) A61C7/146 (EP,US) A61C8/0089 (EP,US) G16H40/63 (EP,US) G16H50/50 (EP,US) A61B2034/102 (EP,US) A61B2034/105 (EP,US) A61B2034/107 (EP,US) A61B2034/2065 (EP,US) A61B2034/252 (EP,US) A61B2090/3612 (EP,US) Y10S901/09 (EP,US) Y10S901/47 (EP,US)	2015-02-26 2017-06-13	2015-02-26	052481028

72. Cross-Fluted Endodontic Instrument

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication	Earliest	IPC	CPC	Publication	Earliest	Family
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Cross-Fluted Endodontic Instrument	HEATH DEREK [US] TREADWAY STEVE [US]	HEATH DEREK [US] TREADWAY STEVE [US]	number US2015056571A1	priority 2013-08-20	A61C5/02	A61C5/42 (EP,US)	date 2015-02-26	publication 2015-02-26	number 052480682
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73. Cross-Fluted Endodontic Instrument

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
Cross-Fluted Endodontic Instrument	HEATH DEREK [US] TREADWAY STEVE [US]	D & S DENTAL LLC [US]	US2017143451A1	2013-08-20	A61C5/42	A61C5/42 (EP,US)	2017-05-25	2017-05-25	058719426

74. MIXING JOINT FOR SYRINGE

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
MIXING JOINT FOR SYRINGE	KIM MIN SUNG [KR] PARK HEE HWAN [KR]	KM [KR] PARK HEE HWAN [KR] KIM MIN SUNG [KR]	KR101353378B1	2013-08-19	A61M5/178 B05B15/00 B05B7/04	A61C5/40 (KR) A61C5/50 (KR) A61C5/60 (KR) B05B15/14 (KR) B05B7/04 (KR)	2014-01-22	2014-01-22	050145994

75. ENDODONTIC POST ASSEMBLY AND METHODS OF PRODUCING AND USING THE SAME

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
ENDODONTIC POST ASSEMBLY AND METHODS OF PRODUCING AND USING THE SAME	LIU PI-YING [TW]	TAIWAN GREEN POINT ENTPR CO [TW]	US2015044640A1	2013-08-08	A61C5/04 B29C45/00 B29C71/00 B65B55/02	A61C5/50 (EP,US) B29C45/0053 (US) B29C2045/0077 (US) B29C2045/2683 (EP,US) B29C37/02 (EP,US) B29C45/26 (EP,US) B29K2101/12 (EP,US) B29L2031/7546 (EP,US)	2015-02-12	2015-02-11	052448954

76. Root Canal Probe Tool and Method of Removing a Broken Instrument Fragment from a Root Canal

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
Root Canal Probe Tool and Method of Removing a Broken Instrument Fragment from a Root Canal	LASNER JEFFREY I [US]	LASNER JEFFREY I [US]	US2015044634A1 US9579166B2	2013-08-07	A61C5/02 A61C1/07	A61C1/07 (EP,US) A61C5/46 (EP,US)	2015-02-12 2017-02-28	2015-02-12	052448952

77. DENTAL ROOT CANAL FILLING MATERIAL CARTRIDGE HAVING BUILT-IN HEATING MECHANISM FOR SOFTENING THE MATERIAL

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
DENTAL ROOT CANAL FILLING MATERIAL CARTRIDGE HAVING BUILT-IN HEATING MECHANISM FOR SOFTENING THE MATERIAL	LI NATHAN Y [US] WU DAQING [CN]	LI NATHAN Y [US] WU DAQING [CN]	US2015079538A1	2013-07-26	A61C5/04	A61C5/55 (EP,US) A61C5/62 (EP,US)	2015-03-19	2015-01-29	051422129

78. NANO BUBBLE GENERATOR FOR CLEANING ROOT CANAL OF TOOTH AND DENTAL APPARATUS COMPRISING THE SAME

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
NANO BUBBLE GENERATOR FOR CLEANING ROOT CANAL OF TOOTH AND DENTAL APPARATUS COMPRISING THE SAME	SUNG JAEYONG [KR] BANG TAEJUN [KR] LEE INWHAN [KR] CHO INJE [KR] SUNG GILHWAN [KR]	B & L BIOTECH INC [KR] B&L BIOTECH INC [KR]	US2015030991A1 US9545295B2	2013-07-25	A61C5/02 B01F3/04 A61C17/20 A61C17/02	A61C17/02 (EP,US) A61C17/20 (EP,US) A61C5/40 (EP,US)	2015-01-29 2017-01-17	2015-01-29	052390793

	BAEK SEUNG KI [KR]								
79. Apparatus for visualizing defects of a dental instrument									
Title Apparatus for visualizing defects of a dental instrument	Inventors PERIC BORISLAVA [DE]	Applicants VDW GMBH [DE]	Publication number EP2829254A1	Earliest priority 2013-07-24	IPC A61C19/04 G01N21/95	CPC A61C19/00 (EP) G01N21/01 (EP) G01N21/95 (EP) A61C19/04 (EP) A61C5/42 (EP) G01N21/9515 (EP)	Publication date 2015-01-28	Earliest publication 2015-01-28	Family number 048917303
80. Endodontic Instrument With Narrow Radial Lands									
Title Endodontic Instrument With Narrow Radial Lands	Inventors JAUNBERZINS ANDRIS [US]	Applicants JAUNBERZINS ANDRIS [US]	Publication number US2017135786A1	Earliest priority 2013-07-18	IPC A61C5/42	CPC A61C5/42 (EP,US) A61C2201/007 (EP,US)	Publication date 2017-05-18	Earliest publication 2017-05-18	Family number 058690201
81. Endodontic Instrument With Narrow Radial Lands									
Title Endodontic Instrument With Narrow Radial Lands	Inventors JAUNBERZINS ANDRIS [US]	Applicants JAUNBERZINS ANDRIS [US]	Publication number US2015024342A1	Earliest priority 2013-07-18	IPC A61C5/02	CPC A61C5/42 (EP,US)	Publication date 2015-01-22	Earliest publication 2015-01-22	Family number 051298977
82. Process for Producing a Shape Memory Spiral Rotary File									
Title Process for Producing a Shape Memory Spiral Rotary File	Inventors SHOTTON VINCENT [US] AMMON DAN [US]	Applicants DENTSPLY INT INC [US]	Publication number US2015164615A1 US9902025B2	Earliest priority 2013-07-11	IPC A61C5/02 A61C5/42 B21K5/12 B23P15/44 B21D37/16	CPC A61C5/42 (EP,US) B21K5/12 (US) B23P15/44 (US) B21D37/16 (US) Y10T29/49826 (EP,US)	Publication date 2015-06-18 2018-02-27	Earliest publication 2015-01-15	Family number 052280654
83. Method and Apparatus for Facial Visualization and Dental or Operational Planning									
Title Method and Apparatus for Facial Visualization and Dental or Operational Planning	Inventors FRIDZON BORIS [IL]	Applicants GOLDINER UREE [IL] FRIDZON BORIS [IL]	Publication number US2016374785A1	Earliest priority 2013-07-07	IPC A61B90/00 A61C13/00 A61C5/77 G16Z99/00	CPC A61B34/10 (US) A61B90/37 (US) A61C13/0004 (EP,US) A61C5/77 (US) G06T11/00 (EP,US) G16H20/40 (US) G16H30/40 (EP,US) G16H50/50 (EP,US) G16Z99/00 (EP,US) A61B2034/107 (US) A61B2090/364 (US) A61B2560/0487 (US) A61C19/10 (EP,US)	Publication date 2016-12-29	Earliest publication 2015-01-15	Family number 049784208
84. COMPOSITIONS AND METHODS FOR DENTAL APPLICATIONS INVOLVING ZINC-OXIDE CEMENTS									
Title COMPOSITIONS AND METHODS FOR DENTAL APPLICATIONS	Inventors GUZMAN JASON [US] WAN JEFFREY [US]	Applicants ESSENTIAL DENTAL	Publication number US2015011452A1 US9757209B2	Earliest priority 2013-07-03	IPC A61C5/02 A61C5/08 B08B3/08	CPC A61C3/16 (EP,US) A61C5/40	Publication date 2015-01-08 2017-09-12	Earliest publication 2015-01-08	Family number 052133213

INVOLVING ZINC- OXIDE CEMENTS		SYSTEMS INC [US]			A61K6/00 C11D7/26 C11D7/32 C11D7/44 A61C3/16 A61C5/40 A61K6/083 C11D1/62 C11D3/20 C11D3/50	(EP,US) A61K6/30 (EP,US) A61K6/60 (EP,US) A61K6/887 (EP,US) C11D1/62 (EP,US) C11D3/2093 (EP,US) C11D3/2096 (EP,US) C11D3/50 (EP,US) C11D7/266 (US) C11D7/3209 (US) C11D7/44 (US) A61K6/887, C08L33/08, INV (EP,US) A61K6/887, C08L33/10, INV (EP,US)			
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85. A METHOD AND SYSTEM FOR THE MANUFACTURING OF AN ORAL TEMPLATE FROM A 3D DIGITAL DATA

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
A METHOD AND SYSTEM FOR THE MANUFACTURING OF AN ORAL TEMPLATE FROM A 3D DIGITAL DATA	SAMRANO SERGIO [IL]	SHALEV MICHAL [IL] SAMRANO SERGIO [IL]	US2016143717A1	2013-06-27	A61B6/03 A61B6/51 A61C1/08 A61C13/00 A61C13/34 A61C5/02 A61C5/42 A61C7/00 A61C7/14	A61B6/032 (US) A61B6/51 (US) A61C1/082 (EP,US) A61C1/084 (EP,US) A61C13/0019 (US) A61C13/34 (US) A61C5/42 (EP,US) A61C7/002 (US) A61C7/146 (US) A61C13/0013 (EP,US) A61C5/44 (EP,US)	2016-05-26	2014-12-31	050436367

86. APPARATUS AND METHODS FOR FILLING TEETH AND ROOT CANALS

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
APPARATUS AND METHODS FOR FILLING TEETH AND ROOT CANALS	KHAKPOUR MEHRZAD [US] BERGHEIM BJARNE [US]	SONENDO INC [US]	US2024207017A1	2013-06-26	A61C1/08 A61C17/02 A61C17/024 A61C17/028 A61C17/20 A61C5/40 A61C5/50 A61C5/62	A61C1/087 (EP,US) A61C17/0202 (EP,US) A61C17/024 (EP,US) A61C17/20 (US) A61C5/40 (EP,US) A61C5/50 (EP,US) A61C5/62 (EP,US) A61C17/028 (EP,US)	2024-06-27	2014-12-31	051220881

87. ENDODONTIC INSTRUMENTS

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
ENDODONTIC INSTRUMENTS	SHOTTON VINCENT [US] AMMON DAN [US]	DENTSPLY INT INC [US] DENTSPLY SIRONA INC [US]	US2015216624A1 US9901418B2	2013-06-20	A61C5/02 A61C5/42	A61C5/42 (EP,US)	2015-08-06 2018-02-27	2014-12-24	052105539

88. ENDODONTIC POST SYSTEM

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
ENDODONTIC POST SYSTEM	YARED GHASSAN [CA] DE-DEUS GUSTAVO [BR]	YARED GHASSAN [CA] DE-DEUS GUSTAVO [BR]	CA2820621A1	2013-06-19	A61C5/40 A61C5/50	A61C5/40 (EP) A61C5/50 (EP)	2014-12-19	2014-12-19	052103729

89. ENDO FILE FOR DENTAL ENDODONTIC TREATMENT

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
ENDO FILE FOR DENTAL ENDODONTIC TREATMENT	KIM HYEONG WOO [KR] KIM GYUN HWAN [KR] KIM SUN YOUNG [KR]	KIM HYEONG WOO [KR] KIM GYUN HWAN [KR] KIM SUN YOUNG [KR]	US10441383B2 US2016128800A1	2013-06-14	A61C5/02 A61C5/42 A61C5/48 A61C5/00	A61C3/00 (KR) A61C5/42 (EP,US) A61C5/48 (EP,US)	2016-05-12 2019-10-15	2013-12-26	049989038

90. ROOT CANAL INSTRUMENT HAVING AN OVOID OR OVAL SECTION

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
ROOT CANAL INSTRUMENT HAVING AN OVOID OR OVAL SECTION	LEVY GUY [FR]	MICRO MEGA INT MFG SA [FR] MICRO MEGA INT MFG SA	US2016113735A1	2013-05-30	A61C5/02 A61C5/42	A61C5/42 (EP,US)	2016-04-28	2014-12-04	049209435

91. Method and apparatus for laser induced thermo-acoustical streaming of liquid

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
Method and apparatus for laser induced thermo-acoustical streaming of liquid	ALTSHULER GREGORY B [US] BELIKOV ANDREI V [RU] SKRYPNIK ALEXEI V [RU]	LASER ABRASIVE TECHNOLOGIES LLC [US] LASER ABRASIVE TECH LLC [US] IPG PHOTONICS CORP [US]	US10130450B2 US2014342303A1	2013-05-14	A61C1/00 A61C17/02 A61C5/50 A61C1/00	A61C1/0046 (EP,US) A61C17/02 (EP,US) A61C17/0202 (EP,US) A61C5/50 (EP,US) A61C1/0069 (EP,US)	2014-11-20 2018-11-20	2014-11-20	051896040

92. COMPOSITIONS FOR ENDODONTIC INSTRUMENTS

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
COMPOSITIONS FOR ENDODONTIC INSTRUMENTS	BERGER TODD [US] WILKINSON KEVIN [US] BARANTZ ADAM [US] AMMON DAN [US] JIN XIAOMING [US] KOLTISKO BERNARD [US]	DENTSPLY INT INC [US] DENTSPLY SIRONA INC [US]	US10004666B2 US2014335475A1	2013-05-07	A61C5/04 A61K6/00 A61K6/884 A61C5/55 A61K6/02	A61C5/55 (EP,US) A61K6/54 (EP,US) A61K6/77 (EP,US) A61K6/816 (EP,US) A61K6/818 (EP,US) A61K6/824 (EP,US) A61K6/54, C08L33/10, INV (EP,US) A61K6/54, C08L7/00, INV (EP,US)	2014-11-13 2018-06-26	2014-11-13	050842388

93. APPARATUS AND METHODS FOR TREATING TEETH

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
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APPARATUS AND METHODS FOR TREATING TEETH	KHAKPOUR MEHRZAD [US] BERGHEIM BJARNE [US] EVANS RYAN [US]	SONENDO INC [US]	US2021038344A1	2013-05-01	A61C1/00 A61C1/08 A61C17/02 A61C17/028 A61C17/20 A61C3/02 A61C5/40 A61C5/42	A61C1/0046 (US) A61C1/082 (US) A61C17/02 (EP,US) A61C17/0202 (EP,US) A61C17/028 (EP,US) A61C3/02 (US) A61C5/40 (EP,US) A61C5/42 (EP,US) A61C17/20 (EP,US)	2021-02-11	2014-11-06	051022415
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94. METHOD FOR PLANNING A ROOT TREATMENT OF A PATIENT

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
METHOD FOR PLANNING A ROOT TREATMENT OF A PATIENT	HEY JOACHIM [DE] KUSCH JOCHEN [DE] ZOLLORSCH ANDREAS [DE]	SICAT GMBH & CO KG [DE]	US10039615B2 US2016030136A1	2013-03-28	A61C13/00 A61C5/02 A61B5/00 A61C1/08 A61C5/40 A61B34/10 A61C5/42 A61C5/44	A61B5/0088 (US) A61C1/082 (EP,US) A61C5/40 (US) A61B2034/105 (EP,US) A61C5/42 (EP,US) A61C5/44 (EP,US)	2016-02-04 2018-08-07	2014-10-02	050424204

95. COMBINED USE OF ULTRASOUND WITH NICKEL TITANIUM ENDODONTIC FILE IN ENDODONTIC PROCEDURE

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
COMBINED USE OF ULTRASOUND WITH NICKEL TITANIUM ENDODONTIC FILE IN ENDODONTIC PROCEDURE	RAMOS CARLOS ALBERTO SPIRONELLI [US] TUTTLE RICHARD D [US]	ULTRADENT PRODUCTS INC [US]	US2016022377A1	2013-03-15	A61C1/07 A61C1/12 A61C1/14 A61C3/03 A61C5/02	A61C1/07 (EP,US) A61C1/12 (US) A61C1/144 (US) A61C1/148 (US) A61C3/03 (EP,US) A61C5/40 (EP,US) A61C5/42 (EP,US)	2016-01-28	2014-09-18	051537620

96. CALCIUM SULFATE-RESIN HYBRID MATERIALS AND METHODS OF USING AND MAKING THE SAME

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
CALCIUM SULFATE-RESIN HYBRID MATERIALS AND METHODS OF USING AND MAKING THE SAME	WHITE SHANE [US] INABA ADAM [US]	UNIV CALIFORNIA [US]	US2016045403A1 US9889071B2	2013-03-15	A61C5/04 A61K6/083 A61L27/44 A61L27/50 C08K3/30 C08K3/36 A61C5/50 A61K33/06	A61C5/50 (EP,US) A61K33/06 (EP,US) A61K6/889 (EP,US) A61L27/446 (EP,US) A61L27/50 (EP,US) A61P19/00 (EP) C08K3/30 (US) C08K3/36 (US) A61L2430/02 (EP,US) C08K2003/3045 (US) A61K6/56, C08L33/08, INV	2016-02-18 2018-02-13	2014-09-18	051537825

						(EP,US) A61K6/887, C08L33/08, INV (EP,US) A61K6/889, C08L33/08, INV (EP,US) A61L27/446, C08L33/10, INV (EP,US)			
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97. YTTRIA-TREATED PORCELAIN VENEER

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
YTTRIA-TREATED PORCELAIN VENEER	PIASCIK JEFFREY ROBERT [US] STONER BRIAN R [US]	RES TRIANGLE INST [US]	US2014272799A1	2013-03-15	A61C13/00 A61C5/77 A61C8/00 A61K6/02	A61C5/77 (EP,US) A61K6/20 (EP,US) A61K6/811 (EP,US) A61K6/818 (EP,US) A61K6/822 (EP,US) A61K6/824 (EP,US)	2014-09-18	2014-09-18	051528589

98. TEAR-RESISTANT DENTAL DAMS

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
TEAR-RESISTANT DENTAL DAMS	WARNER THOMAS P [US] KOTWICKI ALLAN [US]	EASYDAM LLC [US]	US2014272784A1 US9060830B2	2013-03-15	A61C5/12	A61C5/82 (EP,US)	2014-09-18 2015-06-23	2014-09-18	051528577

99. ROOT CANAL FOR TISSUE IN-GROWTH

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
ROOT CANAL FOR TISSUE IN-GROWTH	NEVINS ALAN [US]	NEVINS ALAN [US]	US2014272803A1	2013-03-14	A61C5/02 A61C5/04 A61K6/083	A61C5/42 (EP,US) A61C5/50 (EP,US) A61K6/54 (EP,US) A61K6/69 (EP,US)	2014-09-18	2014-09-18	051528592

100. SYSTEM AND METHOD FOR PROVIDING DENTAL TREATMENT RECOMMENDATIONS

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
SYSTEM AND METHOD FOR PROVIDING DENTAL TREATMENT RECOMMENDATIONS	SUDA GEORGE JOSEPH [US] TA DAN CHI [US] PHAM PHONG TRUNG [US] CLARK MARLIN H [US]	SMILE BRANDS INC [US]	US10529449B2 US2019221302A1	2013-03-14	A61C7/00 G16H10/60 G16H20/40 A61C13/00 A61C5/77	A61C13/0004 (EP,US) A61C7/002 (EP,US) G16H10/60 (EP,US) G16H15/00 (EP,US) G16H20/00 (EP,US) G16H20/40 (US) G16H30/20 (EP,US) G16H40/20 (EP,US) G16H40/67 (EP,US) G16H80/00	2019-07-18 2020-01-07	2019-03-26	065811614

						(EP,US) A61C5/77 (EP,US)			
101. HANDPIECE HAVING A DISPOSABLE HEAD PORTION FOR ROTARY ENDODONTIC FILE									
Title HANDPIECE HAVING A DISPOSABLE HEAD PORTION FOR ROTARY ENDODONTIC FILE	Inventors BECKER ARIK [IL] ROTHENSTEIN SIMON [IL] LEVY HAIM [IL]	Applicants MEDIC NRG LTD [IL]	Publication number WO2014141241A1	Earliest priority 2013-03-12	IPC A61C5/02 A61C5/42	CPC A61C5/42 (EP) A61C1/003 (EP) A61C1/144 (EP) A61C1/186 (EP)	Publication date 2014-09-18	Earliest publication 2014-09-18	Family number 048916408
102. ENDODONTIC INSTRUMENT, IN PARTICULAR FOR REAMING A ROOT CANAL									
Title ENDODONTIC INSTRUMENT, IN PARTICULAR FOR REAMING A ROOT CANAL	Inventors BREGUET OLIVIER [CH] ROSATO GIANLUCA [CH]	Applicants FKG DENTAIRE S A [CH] FKG DENTAIRE SARL [CH]	Publication number US11259895B2 US2016067012A1	Earliest priority 2013-03-12	IPC A61C5/02 A61C5/42	CPC A61C5/42 (EP,US)	Publication date 2016-03-10 2022-03-01	Earliest publication 2014-09-15	Family number 049000742
103. MIRROR, IN PARTICULAR MEDICAL MIRROR, AND DEVICE, IN PARTICULAR FOR ROOT CANAL TREATMENT									
Title MIRROR, IN PARTICULAR MEDICAL MIRROR, AND DEVICE, IN PARTICULAR FOR ROOT CANAL TREATMENT	Inventors WINKELMANN WOLFGANG [DE]	Applicants WINKELMANN WOLFGANG [DE]	Publication number US2016022376A1	Earliest priority 2013-03-07	IPC A61B1/247 A61B17/17 A61C1/08 A61C1/12 A61C5/02 A61C5/04 A61C5/44 A61C5/50	CPC A61B1/247 (EP,US) A61B17/1703 (US) A61C1/082 (EP,US) A61C1/12 (US) A61C19/041 (EP,US) A61C5/44 (EP,US) A61C5/50 (EP,US) A61B2090/3618 (EP,US) A61C5/42 (EP,US)	Publication date 2016-01-28	Earliest publication 2014-04-09	Family number 050556196
104. SYSTEM AND METHOD FOR ACOUSTICAL ENDODONTICS									
Title SYSTEM AND METHOD FOR ACOUSTICAL ENDODONTICS	Inventors JOLESZ FERENC A [US] WHITE PHILLIP JASON [US] CLEMENT GREGORY THOMAS [US] MCDANNOLD NATHAN [US] PAGONIS TOM C [US] ADAMS DOUGLASS [US]	Applicants BRIGHAM & WOMENS HOSPITAL [US] NEWPORT ENDODONTICS P C [US]	Publication number US2016015478A1	Earliest priority 2013-03-07	IPC A61B8/08 A61C1/00 A61C1/07 A61C5/02	CPC A61B8/0875 (US) A61C1/0015 (US) A61C1/07 (US) A61C5/40 (EP,US) A61N2007/0026 (US) A61N2007/0052 (US) A61N2007/0078 (US)	Publication date 2016-01-21	Earliest publication 2014-09-12	Family number 051491820
105. DENTAL IMAGE DISPLAY DEVICE, DENTAL SURGICAL OPERATION DEVICE, AND DENTAL IMAGE DISPLAY METHOD									
Title DENTAL IMAGE DISPLAY DEVICE, DENTAL SURGICAL OPERATION DEVICE, AND DENTAL IMAGE DISPLAY METHOD	Inventors FLEER JÜRGEN RICHARD [DE] NAKAI TERUJI [JP] SUZUKI MASAKAZU [JP] SADAKANE TOMOYUKI [JP]	Applicants MORITA MFG [JP] J MORITA MFG CORP [JP]	Publication number US10204443B2 US2014342301A1	Earliest priority 2013-03-06	IPC A61C5/02 A61B6/51 G06T15/08 A61B5/00 A61B6/03 A61C5/44 A61B5/055	CPC A61B5/0088 (EP,US) A61B5/4547 (EP,US) A61B6/032 (EP,US) A61B6/463 (EP,US) A61B6/51	Publication date 2014-11-20 2019-02-12	Earliest publication 2014-09-10	Family number 050679820

						(EP,US) A61B6/5247 (EP,US) A61C5/44 (EP,US) G06T15/08 (US) A61B5/0066 (EP,US) A61B5/055 (EP) A61B5/4542 (EP,US) G06T2200/04 (US) G06T2215/16 (US)			
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106. Schraubenzieher für eine zahnmedizinische Zahnschraube

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
Schraubenzieher für eine zahnmedizinische Zahnschraube			DE202013002050U1	2013-03-01	A61C13/263	A61C3/00 (EP) A61C5/35 (EP)	2013-04-09	2013-04-09	048288271

107. Oral Care System and Method

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
Oral Care System and Method	DOWNNS RICHARD D [US]	DOWNNS RICHARD D [US]	US2014242551A1	2013-02-28	A61C19/06 A61C5/02 A61C5/04 A61K6/00	A61C17/02 (EP,US) A61C19/066 (US) A61C5/50 (EP,US) A61K6/52 (EP,US) A61K8/20 (EP,US) A61Q11/00 (EP,US) A61C1/0046 (EP,US) A61C17/20 (EP,US) A61C19/063 (EP,US)	2014-08-28	2014-08-28	051388498

108. PROCESS OF MAKING MULTI-TAPER DENTAL ROOT CANAL FILLING POINTS/CONES

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
PROCESS OF MAKING MULTI-TAPER DENTAL ROOT CANAL FILLING POINTS/CONES	LI NATHAN Y [US] WU DAQING [US]	LI NATHAN Y [US] TULSA DENTAL PRODUCTS LLC [US]	EP2958510A1 EP2958510B1	2013-02-21	A61C5/50	A61C5/50 (EP)	2015-12-30 2020-04-15	2014-08-28	050342469

109. MULTI-TAPER DENTAL ROOT CANAL FILLING POINTS/CONES AND PROCESS OF MAKING SAME

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
MULTI-TAPER DENTAL ROOT CANAL FILLING POINTS/CONES AND PROCESS OF MAKING SAME	LI NATHAN Y [US] WU DAQING [CN]	LI NATHAN Y [US] WU DAQING [CN]	US2014272802A1	2013-02-21	A61C13/00 A61C5/04	A61C5/50 (EP,US)	2014-09-18	2014-09-18	051528591

110. MULTI-TAPER DENTAL ROOT CANAL FILLING POINTS/CONES AND PROCESS OF MAKING SAME

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
MULTI-TAPER DENTAL ROOT CANAL FILLING POINTS/CONES AND PROCESS OF MAKING SAME	LI NATHAN Y [US]	DENTSPLY SIRONA INC [US]	US2020129269A1	2013-02-21	A61C5/55	A61C13/206 (US) A61C5/50 (EP) A61C5/55 (US)	2020-04-30	2020-04-30	070327474

111. Dentales Absauginstrument

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
Dentales Absauginstrument		COLTENE WHALEEDENT GMBH & CO KG [DE]	DE202013001607U1	2013-02-19	A61C17/06	A61C17/08 (EP) A61C5/40 (EP)	2013-03-08	2013-03-08	048084833

112. MOLDED DENTAL ROOT CANAL FILLING POINTS/CONES AND PROCESS OF MAKING SAME

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
MOLDED DENTAL ROOT CANAL FILLING POINTS/CONES AND PROCESS OF MAKING SAME	LI NATHAN Y [US] WU [US] DAQING [CN]	LI NATHAN Y [US] WU [US] DAQING [CN] TULSA DENTAL PRODUCTS LLC [US]	US10485633B2 US2014315155A1	2013-02-14	A61C13/00 A61C5/04 A61C13/20 A61C5/50	A61C13/206 (EP,US) A61C5/50 (EP,US) A61C13/20 (EP,US)	2014-10-23 2019-11-26	2014-08-21	051354695

113. Endodontic rotary file system having smaller diameter non-landed files and medium-to-larger diameter files with landed and non-landed portions

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
Endodontic rotary file system having smaller diameter non-landed files and medium-to-larger diameter files with landed and non-landed portions	MAUPIN CHARLES [US]	MAUPIN CHARLES [US]	US9681928B1	2013-02-11		A61C5/42 (EP,US)	2017-06-20	2017-06-20	059033825

114. DEVICE FOR ENDODONTICS BY MEANS OF CONTINUOUS ULTRASONIC IRRIGATION

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
DEVICE FOR ENDODONTICS BY MEANS OF CONTINUOUS ULTRASONIC IRRIGATION	CASTELO BAZ PABLO [ES] VARELA PATIÑO PURIFICACION [ES] MARTIN BIEDMA BENJAMIN [ES] RUIZ PIÑON MANUEL [ES] RIVAS MUNDIÑA BERTA [ES]	UNIV SANTIAGO COMPOSTELA [ES]	US2016067023A1	2013-02-11	A61C17/06 A61C17/20 A61C5/02 A61C5/40	A61C17/02 (EP,US) A61C17/0208 (EP,US) A61C17/08 (EP,US) A61C17/20 (EP,ES,US) A61C5/40 (EP,US)	2016-03-10	2014-08-12	051267105

115. DENTAL TREATMENT SYSTEM

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
DENTAL TREATMENT SYSTEM	BERGHEIM BJARNE [US] KHAKPOUR MEHRZAD [US] CHEN JENNIFER [US] DECHELETTE ALEXIS [US]	SONENDO INC [US]	US2020297455A1	2013-02-04	A61C1/00 A61C1/08 A61C17/02 A61C17/028 A61C5/40	A61C1/0061 (EP,US) A61C1/087 (EP,US) A61C17/0202 (EP,US) A61C17/0217 (EP,US) A61C17/024 (EP,US) A61C17/028 (EP,US) A61C5/40 (EP,US)	2020-09-24	2014-08-07	050185024

						A61C2204/005 (EP,US)			
116. ENDODONTIC CLEANING INSTRUMENT AND APPARATUS									
Title ENDODONTIC CLEANING INSTRUMENT AND APPARATUS	Inventors YARED GHASSAN [CA]	Applicants YARED GHASSAN [CA]	Publication number US2014212834A1	Earliest priority 2013-01-31	IPC A61C5/40 A61C5/42	CPC A61C17/0202 (EP,US) A61C5/40 (EP,US)	Publication date 2014-07-31	Earliest publication 2014-07-31	Family number 051223300
117. INSTRUMENT FOR DRILLING DENTAL ROOT CANALS									
Title INSTRUMENT FOR DRILLING DENTAL ROOT CANALS	Inventors ROTA GILBERT [FR] VALLOTTON PAUL-HENRI [CH]	Applicants DENTSPLY SIRONA INC [US]	Publication number US10123850B2 US2018008374A1	Earliest priority 2013-01-30	IPC A61C5/40 A61C5/42	CPC A61C5/40 (US) A61C5/42 (EP,US)	Publication date 2018-01-11 2018-11-13	Earliest publication 2014-08-07	Family number 047833310
118. scale for working length of root canal file									
Title scale for working length of root canal file	Inventors YU NINGNA GUO JIAPING WANG LINHU DONG QINGSHAN	Applicants WUHAN GENERAL HOSPITAL OF GUANGZHOU MILITARY	Publication number CN203053419U	Earliest priority 2013-01-29	IPC G01B21/02	CPC A61C5/44 (EP)	Publication date 2013-07-10	Earliest publication 2013-07-10	Family number 048736363
119. ULTRASONIC TIP ASSEMBLY									
Title ULTRASONIC TIP ASSEMBLY	Inventors MAXWELL RANDALL [US] WILKINSON KEVIN [US]	Applicants DENTSPLY SIRONA INC [US]	Publication number US10130451B2 US2018036105A1	Earliest priority 2013-01-24	IPC A61C17/02 A61C3/03 A61C5/42 A61C5/00 A61C17/06	CPC A61C17/0202 (US) A61C17/0208 (EP,US) A61C17/024 (EP,US) A61C5/42 (EP,US) A61C17/08 (EP,US)	Publication date 2018-02-08 2018-11-20	Earliest publication 2014-07-31	Family number 050151365
120. Dual Wavelength Endodontic Treatment									
Title Dual Wavelength Endodontic Treatment	Inventors BOUTOUSOV DMITRI [US] SIVRIVER ALINA [US] NETCHITAILO VLADIMIR [US]	Applicants BIOLASE INC [US]	Publication number US2014205965A1	Earliest priority 2013-01-22	IPC A61C1/00 A61C5/02 A61N5/06	CPC A61C1/0046 (EP,US) A61C17/02 (EP,US) A61C5/40 (EP,US) A61N5/0624 (EP,US) A61N2005/0606 (EP,US)	Publication date 2014-07-24	Earliest publication 2014-07-24	Family number 051207954
121. ROOT CANAL FILLING APPARATUS INTEGRATED PLUNGER									
Title ROOT CANAL FILLING APPARATUS INTEGRATED PLUNGER	Inventors RYU HYEON SEOCK [KR]	Applicants DENTI INC S [KR]	Publication number KR101440379B1 KR20140087448A	Earliest priority 2012-12-31	IPC A61C3/08 A61C5/04 A61M5/145	CPC A61C3/08 (KR) A61C5/55 (KR) A61C5/62 (KR)	Publication date 2014-07-09 2014-09-17	Earliest publication 2014-07-09	Family number 051736368
122. DENTAL ROTARY FILE HAVING DISTINGUISHABLE MARK									
Title DENTAL ROTARY FILE HAVING DISTINGUISHABLE MARK	Inventors YOU JAE HOON [CA]	Applicants DIADENT GROUP INTERNAT [KR]	Publication number KR101953889B1 KR20140086443A	Earliest priority 2012-12-28	IPC A61C5/02 A61C1/08 A61C3/02	CPC A61C5/42 (KR) A61C5/44 (KR) A61C2201/002 (KR)	Publication date 2014-07-08 2019-03-04	Earliest publication 2014-07-08	Family number 051735730
123. APPARATUS AND METHODS FOR CLEANING TEETH AND ROOT CANALS									

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
APPARATUS AND METHODS FOR CLEANING TEETH AND ROOT CANALS	KHAKPOUR MEHRZAD [US] BERGHEIM BJARNE [US] TEBBS RICHARD S [US] GHARIB MORTEZA [US] PHAM MICHELE [US]	SONENDO INC [US]	US11213375B2 US2014220505A1	2012-12-20	A61C5/02 A61C17/02 A61C5/40 A61C17/20	A61C17/02 (EP,US) A61C17/0202 (US) A61C5/40 (EP,US) A61C17/20 (EP,US)	2014-08-07 2022-01-04	2014-06-26	050023856

124. APPARATUS AND METHODS FOR CLEANING TEETH AND ROOT CANALS

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
APPARATUS AND METHODS FOR CLEANING TEETH AND ROOT CANALS	KHAKPOUR MEHRZAD [US] BERGHEIM BJARNE [US] EVANS RYAN [US]	SONENDO INC [US]	US2021386532A1	2012-12-20	A61C17/02 A61C17/024 A61C17/20 A61C5/40	A61C17/0202 (EP,US) A61C17/0208 (EP,US) A61C17/024 (EP,US) A61C17/20 (EP,US) A61C5/40 (EP,US)	2021-12-16	2016-04-07	055631946

125. Preparation method of personalized and integrated all-ceramic post-and-core of dentistry

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
Preparation method of personalized and integrated all-ceramic post-and-core of dentistry	ZHOU TUANFENG WANG XINZHI	UNIV PEKING SCHOOL STOMATOLOGY	CN103083094A CN103083094B	2012-12-20	A61C5/77 G06F17/50	A61C13/0004 (EP,US) A61C13/30 (EP) A61C5/77 (EP,US) G16H20/40 (US)	2013-05-08 2015-10-21	2013-05-08	048196588

126. ENDODONTIC SUPPORTING PIN AND RELATED CONNECTOR

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
ENDODONTIC SUPPORTING PIN AND RELATED CONNECTOR	TONINI RICCARDO [IT]	TONINI RICCARDO [IT]	EP2934371A1 EP2934371B1	2012-12-18	A61C5/04 A61C13/30 A61C5/35 A61C5/50	A61C13/30 (EP) A61C5/35 (EP) A61C5/50 (EP)	2015-10-28 2019-07-10	2014-06-19	047720599

127. ELECTRICAL DISCHARGE IRRIGATOR APPARATUS AND METHOD

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
ELECTRICAL DISCHARGE IRRIGATOR APPARATUS AND METHOD	FREGOSO GILBERT [US] HECKERMAN BRAD [US] AVNIEL YUVAL CHARLES [US]	AMERICAN EAGLE INSTR INC [US] G&H TECH LLC [US]	EP2931175A1 EP2931175A4 EP2931175B1	2012-12-17	A61C5/02 A61C17/02 A61C19/06 A61M3/02 A61N1/05 A61N1/18 A61N1/44	A61C17/024 (EP,US) A61C19/063 (EP) A61C5/40 (EP) A61M3/0233 (EP,US) A61N1/0548 (EP) A61N1/44 (EP,US) A61M3/0202 (EP,US)	2015-10-21 2016-08-24 2020-09-02	2014-06-26	050979436

128. ENDODONTIC TOOL WITH ROTATIONAL AND AXIAL RECIPROCATION

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
ENDODONTIC TOOL WITH ROTATIONAL AND AXIAL RECIPROCATION	YARED GHASSAN [CA]	YARED GHASSAN [CA]	US2015374458A1	2012-12-13	A61C1/18 A61C3/02 A61C5/40 A61C5/42	A61C1/02 (EP,US) A61C1/188 (US) A61C3/02 (US) A61C5/40 (EP,US) A61C5/42	2015-12-31	2014-06-13	050929128

						(EP,US) A61C5/48 (EP) A61C1/141 (EP,US)			
129. DENTAL LASER-EMITTING DEVICE AND METHODS									
Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
DENTAL LASER-EMITTING DEVICE AND METHODS	MILLER ALAN [US] WACLAWIK BART [US] PARKER WILLIAM S [US]	MILLER ALAN [US] WACLAWIK BART [US] PARKER WILLIAM S [US] DENTSPLY INT INC [US]	US2014170588A1	2012-12-13	A61B10/02 A61B18/20 A61C1/00 A61C17/02 A61C3/02 A61C5/02 A61C8/00 A61N5/06	A61B10/02 (EP,US) A61C1/0046 (EP,US) A61C1/0092 (US) A61C17/0202 (EP,US) A61C3/02 (US) A61C8/0089 (US) A61N5/067 (EP) A61B18/201 (EP,US) A61B2018/00565 (EP,US) A61B2018/00577 (EP,US) A61B2018/00589 (EP,US) A61B2018/00601 (EP,US) A61B2018/00642 (EP,US) A61B2018/00708 (EP,US) A61B2018/2025 (EP,US) A61B2018/2065 (EP,US) A61C1/0023 (EP,US) A61C5/40 (EP,US) A61N5/067 (US)	2014-06-19	2014-06-19	050931309
130. DETECTION OF CARIOUS DENTIN TISSUE AND REMOVAL THEREOF BY MEANS OF A DENTAL INSTRUMENT									
Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
DETECTION OF CARIOUS DENTIN TISSUE AND REMOVAL THEREOF BY MEANS OF A DENTAL INSTRUMENT	ALMHÖJD ULRICA [SE] NILSSON ÅKE [SE] FLORBERGER FREDRIK [SE] HANSSEN KENTH [SE]	RLS GLOBAL AB [SE]	US2015313801A1	2012-11-30	A61B5/00 A61C19/06 A61C3/02 A61C5/02 A61C5/42 A61K6/00 G01N21/35 G01N23/225 G01N33/483	A61B5/0088 (EP,US) A61B5/4547 (US) A61C19/063 (US) A61C3/02 (EP,US) A61C5/42 (EP,US) A61K6/25 (EP,US) A61K6/66 (EP,US) G01N21/35 (US) G01N23/2258 (EP,US) G01N33/4833 (EP,US) G01N2021/3595 (US)	2015-11-05	2014-06-05	050829325
131. Modifizierter Drahtschlingen-Fragmententferner zur Entfernung von frakturierten Wurzelkanalinstrumenten und Stiften aus Zahnwur									

zelkanälen mit Hilfe einer Doppelkanülen - Drahtschlingentechnik (Zahnmedizinisches Gerät)

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
Modifizierter Drahtschlingen-Fragmententferner zur Entfernung von frakturierten Wurzelkanalinstrumenten und Stiften aus Zahnwurzelkanälen mit Hilfe einer Doppelkanülen - Drahtschlingentechnik (Zahnmedizinisches Gerät)		LEINWEBER MARCUS [DE]	DE202012011309U1	2012-11-26	A61C5/02 A61C5/46	A61C5/46 (EP)	2012-12-19	2012-12-19	047554543

132. COMPOUND REINFORCED WITH GLASS OR QUARTZ FIBER AND LIGHT CURING LIQUID RESIN, METHOD FOR THE RECONSTRUCTION OF TEETH AND METHOD OF APPLICATION FOR THE COMPOUND

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
COMPOUND REINFORCED WITH GLASS OR QUARTZ FIBER AND LIGHT CURING LIQUID RESIN, METHOD FOR THE RECONSTRUCTION OF TEETH AND METHOD OF APPLICATION FOR THE COMPOUND	RODRÍGUEZ POSADA MARIO ALBERTO [CR]	RODRÍGUEZ POSADA MARIO ALBERTO [CR]	US2015342713A1	2012-11-08	A61C13/15 A61C13/271 A61C5/00 A61C5/08 A61K6/027 A61K6/083 C03C13/06 C03C14/00 C03C4/00 C08L33/06	A61C13/26 (US) A61C19/003 (US) A61C5/70 (EP,US) A61C5/73 (US) A61K6/62 (EP,US) A61K6/77 (EP,US) A61K6/836 (EP,US) A61K6/887 (EP,US) C03C13/06 (US) C03C14/00 (US) C03C4/0021 (US) C08L33/068 (US) C03C2214/12 (US) A61K6/30, C08L33/10, INV (EP,US)	2015-12-03	2014-05-15	050684080

133. NEEDLE MEMBER FOR FILLING ROOT CANAL

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
NEEDLE MEMBER FOR FILLING ROOT CANAL	RYU HYEON SEOCK [KR]	DENTI INC S [KR]	KR101399075B1 KR20140058071A	2012-11-06	A61C5/04 A61M5/158	A61C5/40 (KR) A61C5/50 (KR) A61M5/158 (KR) A61M2210/0637 (KR)	2014-05-14 2014-05-27	2014-05-14	050888552

134. COMPOSITION AND METHOD OF USING MEDICAMENT FOR ENDODONTIC IRRIGATION, STEM CELL PREPARATIONS AND TISSUE REGENERATION

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
COMPOSITION AND METHOD OF USING MEDICAMENT FOR ENDODONTIC IRRIGATION, STEM CELL PREPARATIONS AND TISSUE REGENERATION	DUKOFF AMY [US]	DUKOFF AMY [US]	US2014113254A1 US9717657B2	2012-10-24	A61B17/88 A61C5/04 A61K6/00 A61C5/50	A61C5/50 (EP,US) A61K6/52 (EP,US) A61K6/56 (EP,US)	2014-04-24 2017-08-01	2014-04-24	050485647

135. Composition and Method for Using Medicament for Endodontic Irrigation, Stem Cell Preparation and Tissue Regeneration

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number

Composition and Method for Using Medicament for Endodontic Irrigation, Stem Cell Preparation and Tissue Regeneration	DUKOFF AMY [US]	DUKOFF AMY [US]	US10226403B2 US2017304157A1	2012-10-24	A61C5/40 A61C5/50 A61K6/00	A61C5/40 (EP,US) A61C5/50 (EP,US) A61K6/50 (EP,US) A61K6/52 (EP,US) A61K6/56 (EP,US)	2017-10-26 2019-03-12	2017-10-26	060089298
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136. COMPOSITION AND METHOD OF USING MEDICAMENT FOR ENDODONTIC IRRIGATION, STEM CELL PREPARATIONS AND TISSUE REGENERATION

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
COMPOSITION AND METHOD OF USING MEDICAMENT FOR ENDODONTIC IRRIGATION, STEM CELL PREPARATIONS AND TISSUE REGENERATION	DUKOFF-TORO AMY [US] DUKOFF AMY [US]	DUKOFF-TORO AMY [US] DUKOFF AMY [US]	US2014335477A1 US8961180B2	2012-10-24	A61C5/02 A61K6/00 A61B17/88 A61C5/04	A61C5/40 (EP,US) A61C5/50 (EP,US) A61K6/50 (EP,US) A61K6/52 (EP,US) A61K6/56 (EP,US)	2014-11-13 2015-02-24	2014-11-13	051865020

137. CANNULA WITH A CLOSED TIP AND RADIAL OPENINGS

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
CANNULA WITH A CLOSED TIP AND RADIAL OPENINGS	FEHLMANN MARC [CH] BRENDLEN DAVID [CH]	PROD DENTAIRES S A [CH]	WO2014060985A2 WO2014060985A3	2012-10-19	A61C17/02	A61C17/024 (EP,US) A61C5/50 (EP)	2014-04-24 2014-07-31	2014-04-24	049943419

138. Drahtschlingen-Fragmententferner zur Entfernung von frakturierten Wurzelkanalinstrumenten und Stiften aus Zahnwurzelkanälen mit Hilfe einer Drahtschlingentechnik (zahnmedizinisches Gerät)

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
Drahtschlingen-Fragmententferner zur Entfernung von frakturierten Wurzelkanalinstrumenten und Stiften aus Zahnwurzelkanälen mit Hilfe einer Drahtschlingentechnik (zahnmedizinisches Gerät)		LEINWEBER MARCUS [DE]	DE202012009599U1	2012-10-06	A61C5/02 A61C5/46	A61C5/46 (EP)	2012-12-11	2012-12-11	047503457

139. Device and method for the application of light-curing composites

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
Device and method for the application of light-curing composites	GENTE MICHAEL PROF DUDDA SIMONE PESCHKE ARNDT ROHNER GOTTFRIED SALZ ULRICH FACHER ANDREAS	IVOCLAR VIVADENT AG	CN105611895A	2012-09-18	A61C13/15 A61C5/06 A61C5/55 A61C5/62	A61B1/04 (US) A61B1/24 (US) A61B17/8836 (EP,US) A61B5/0088 (US) A61B5/4839 (US) A61B5/7405 (US) A61C1/0015 (US) A61C1/0046 (US) A61C1/06 (US) A61C1/088 (US) A61C19/004 (EP,US) A61C5/55 (US) A61C5/62	2016-05-25	2014-03-20	049226161

						(EP,US) A61B1/06 (US)			
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140. DENTAL MICRO-TORNADO TISSUE CUTTING AND REMOVAL METHOD AND APPARATUS

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
DENTAL MICRO-TORNADO TISSUE CUTTING AND REMOVAL METHOD AND APPARATUS	LAUFER ZOHAR [US]	LAUFER ZOHAR [US]	US2014080090A1 US9084651B2	2012-09-17	A61C1/00 A61C17/02 A61C17/06 A61C3/025 A61C5/02 A61C1/00	A61C17/0208 (EP,US) A61C3/025 (EP,US) A61C5/40 (EP,US) A61C1/0061 (EP,US)	2014-03-20 2015-07-21	2014-03-20	050274836

141. ELECTRICAL DISCHARGE IRRIGATOR APPARATUS AND METHOD

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
ELECTRICAL DISCHARGE IRRIGATOR APPARATUS AND METHOD	FREGOSO GILBERT [US] HECKERMAN BRAD [US] AVNIEL YUVAL CHARLES [US] MEUCHEL DENNIS [US]	AMERICAN EAGLE INSTR INC [US] G&H TECH LLC [US]	US11129698B2 US2016228690A1	2012-09-11	A61C5/04 A61C17/16 A61N1/04 A61N1/05 A61N1/30 A61B18/04 A61C1/06 A61C1/07 A61C17/02 A61C17/20 A61C19/06 A61C3/00 A61C5/40 A61C5/50 A61L2/00 A61L2/025 A61L2/10 A61L2/14 A61L2/18 A61L2/22 A61N1/32 A61N1/44 A61N5/06	A61B18/042 (US) A61C1/06 (EP,US) A61C1/07 (EP,US) A61C17/0202 (EP,US) A61C17/16 (US) A61C17/20 (EP,US) A61C19/063 (EP,US) A61C3/00 A61C3/00 (EP,US) A61C5/40 (EP,US) A61C5/50 (US) A61L2/025 (EP,US) A61L2/10 (EP,US) A61L2/14 (EP,US) A61L2/18 (EP,US) A61L2/14 (EP,US) A61L2/18 (EP,US) A61N1/04 (US) A61N1/0448 (US) A61N1/0548 (EP,US) A61N1/306 (US) A61N1/325 (US) A61N1/44 (US) A61N5/0603 (EP,US) G06F3/165 (US) H04S3/008 (US) H04S7/304 (US) A61B2217/007 (US) A61L2/00 (US) A61L2/22 (EP,US) A61L2103/05 (EP,US) A61L2103/75 (EP,US) A61N2005/0606 (EP,US) A61N2005/0661 (EP,US) F04C2270/0421	2016-08-11 2021-09-28	2014-03-20	050278579

						(EP,US) H04S2400/01 (US) H04S2400/03 (US) H04S2400/11 (US)			
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142. ELECTRICAL DISCHARGE IRRIGATOR APPARATUS AND METHOD

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
ELECTRICAL DISCHARGE IRRIGATOR APPARATUS AND METHOD	FREGOSO GILBERT [US] HECKERMAN BRAD B [US]	G & H TECH LLC [US] G&H TECH LLC [US]	US10898705B2 US2019269902A1	2012-09-11	A61B18/04 A61C1/06 A61C1/07 A61C17/02 A61C17/16 A61C17/20 A61C19/06 A61C3/00 A61C3/03 A61C5/40 A61C5/50 A61L2/025 A61L2/10 A61L2/14 A61L2/18 A61N1/04 A61N1/05 A61N1/30 A61N1/32 A61N1/44 A61N5/06 A61L2/00 A61L2/22	A61B18/042 (US) A61C1/06 (US) A61C1/07 (US) A61C17/0202 (US) A61C17/16 (US) A61C17/20 (US) A61C19/063 (US) A61C3/00 (US) A61C3/03 (US) A61C5/40 (EP,US) A61C5/50 (US) A61L2/025 (US) A61L2/10 (US) A61L2/14 (US) A61L2/18 (US) A61N1/04 (US) A61N1/04 (US) A61N1/0448 (US) A61N1/0548 (US) A61N1/306 (US) A61N1/325 (US) A61N1/44 (US) A61N5/0603 (US) A61N7/00 (EP) A61B2018/1213 (EP) A61B2018/1286 (EP) A61B2217/007 (EP,US) A61B2218/002 (EP) A61L2/00 (US) A61L2/025 (EP) A61L2/10 (EP) A61L2/22 (US) A61L2103/05 (EP,US) A61L2103/75 (US) A61N2005/0606 (EP,US) A61N2005/0661 (EP,US) A61N5/0603 (EP) F04C2270/0421 (US)	2019-09-05 2021-01-26	2019-09-05	067767554

143. ENDODONTIC TOOL AND METHOD

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
ENDODONTIC TOOL AND METHOD	YARED GHASSAN [CA]	YARED GHASSAN [US]	US2015216623A1 US9724172B2	2012-09-07	A61C1/14 A61C1/18 A61C5/40	A61C1/0007 (EP,US) A61C1/003 (US)	2015-08-06 2017-08-08	2014-03-07	050231602

		YARED GHASSAN [CA]			A61C1/00 A61C1/08 A61C1/12 A61C5/42	A61C1/06 (US) A61C1/08 (EP,US) A61C1/12 (EP,US) A61C1/14 (US) A61C1/186 (EP,US) A61C5/40 (EP,US) A61C5/42 (EP,US) A61C5/48 (EP)			
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144. INSERT FOR ULTRASONIC IRRIGATION TO BE ENGAGED IN A DENTAL ULTRASOUND DEVICE

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
INSERT FOR ULTRASONIC IRRIGATION TO BE ENGAGED IN A DENTAL ULTRASOUND DEVICE	CAPELLI ALEXANDRE [BR]	CAPELLI ALEXANDRE [BR]	US2014057225A1	2012-08-23	A61C17/20	A61C17/02 (EP,US) A61C17/20 (EP,US) A61C5/40 (EP,US)	2014-02-27	2014-02-26	048985581

145. DEVICE FOR DRYING ROOT CANALS

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
DEVICE FOR DRYING ROOT CANALS	TILSE RAINER [DE]	TILSE RAINER [DE]	US2015157432A1 US9788923B2	2012-08-20	A61C5/04 A61C17/02 A61C17/022 A61C5/40 A61C5/55	A61C17/0202 (US) A61C17/022 (US) A61C5/40 (EP,US) A61C5/55 (EP,US)	2015-06-11 2017-10-17	2014-02-20	049000922

146. ACCESSORIO PER MACCHINE ENDODONTICHE

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
ACCESSORIO PER MACCHINE ENDODONTICHE	PERANTONI EMANUELE VIGNOLETTI GIANFRANCO	PERANTONI EMANUELE VIGNOLETTI GIANFRANCO	ITVR20120167A1	2012-08-10		A61C1/003 (EP) A61C1/18 (EP) A61C5/40 (EP)	2014-02-11	2014-02-11	046939909

147. Dental blank comprising a pre-sintered porous zirconia material, process of its production and dental article formed from said dental blank

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
Dental blank comprising a pre-sintered porous zirconia material, process of its production and dental article formed from said dental blank	HAUPTMANN HOLGER SCHMITTNER SYBILLE S SCHECHNER GALLUS KOLB BRANT U HERRMANN ANDREAS	3M INNOVATIVE PROPERTIES CO	CN104717937A CN104717937B	2012-08-03	A61C13/00 A61C5/77 A61K6/818	A61C13/0006 (RU,US) A61C13/0022 (EP,RU,US) A61C13/01 (RU,US) A61C13/08 (RU,US) A61C5/77 (EP,US) A61C7/00 (US) A61C8/0001 (US) A61C8/005 (US) A61K6/80 (RU) B82Y30/00 (EP,US) C04B35/48 (RU,US) C04B35/486 (EP,US) C04B35/6263 (EP,US)	2015-06-17 2016-11-09	2014-02-05	048949278

						C04B35/6269 (EP,US) C04B35/632 (EP,US) C04B35/63424 (EP,US) C04B35/63488 (EP,US) C04B35/638 (EP,US) C04B38/0045 (EP,RU,US) C04B2111/00836 (EP,US) C04B2235/3217 (EP,US) C04B2235/3225 (EP,US) C04B2235/3227 (EP,US) C04B2235/3248 (EP,US) C04B2235/449 (EP,US) C04B2235/5409 (EP,US) C04B2235/5454 (EP,US) C04B2235/6023 (EP,US) C04B2235/612 (EP,US) C04B2235/6562 (EP,US) C04B2235/6565 (EP,US) C04B2235/6567 (EP,US) C04B2235/781 (EP,US) C04B2235/945 (EP,US) C04B2235/95 (EP,US) C04B2235/96 (EP,US) F04C2270/041 (EP) Y10T428/21 (EP,US) Y10T428/24479 (EP,US) Y10T428/2457 (EP,US) C04B38/0045, C04B35/48, INV (EP,US)		
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148. Translucency enhancing solution for zirconia ceramics

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
Translucency enhancing solution for zirconia ceramics	HAUPTMANN HOLGER HERRMANN	3M INNOVATIVE PROPERTIES CO	CN104918577A CN104918577B	2012-08-03	A61C13/00 A61C5/77 C04B35/486	A61C13/0006 (US) A61C13/01 (US) A61C13/082	2015-09-16 2018-10-23	2014-02-06	047913600

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 C04B41/50 A61C7/12 (US)
 C04B35/48 (US)
 C04B35/486
 (EP,US)
 C04B35/624
 (EP,US)
 C04B35/6263
 (EP) C04B35/632
 (EP) C04B35/638
 (EP)
 C04B38/0045
 (EP,US)
 C04B41/009
 (EP,US)
 C04B41/501
 (EP,US)
 C04B41/85
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						C04B2235/6565 (EP,US) C04B2235/6567 (EP,US) C04B2235/661 (EP,US) C04B2235/72 (EP) C04B2235/95 (EP) C04B2235/96 (EP) C04B2235/9653 (EP,US) Y10T428/24997 (EP,US) C04B38/0045, C04B35/48, INV (EP,US) C04B41/009, C04B35/48, INV (EP,US) C04B41/501, C04B41/4535, C04B2103/0021, C04B2103/0094, INV (EP,US)			
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149. CANAL SIZE MEASURING GUAGE

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
CANAL SIZE MEASURING GUAGE	CHO SIN YEON [KR] JUNG IL YOUNG [KR]	UNIV YONSEI IACF [KR]	KR101372387B1 KR20140016632A	2012-07-30	A61C19/04 A61C5/04	A61C19/041 (KR) A61C5/44 (KR)	2014-02-10 2014-03-12	2014-02-10	050265590

150. ULTRA-FINE GRAIN NICKEL-TITANIUM ALLOY ROOT CANAL FILE AND PREPARATION METHOD THEREFOR

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
ULTRA-FINE GRAIN NICKEL-TITANIUM ALLOY ROOT CANAL FILE AND PREPARATION METHOD THEREFOR	ZHENG YUFENG [CN] ZHOU HUIMIN [CN] LI LI [CN] TONG YUNXIANG [CN]	UNIV HARBIN ENG [CN]	WO2014015767A1	2012-07-24	A61C5/02 A61C5/42 C22F1/00 C22F1/10 C22F1/18	A61C5/42 (EP) C22C14/00 (EP) C22C19/03 (EP) A61C2201/007 (EP)	2014-01-30	2012-10-24	047023980

151. METHOD FOR DIGITAL ARCHIVING AND MANUFACTURING OF DENTAL PROSTHETICS AND PROSTHESIS, AND TEACHING AND TRAINING FOR SAME

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
METHOD FOR DIGITAL ARCHIVING AND MANUFACTURING OF DENTAL PROSTHETICS AND PROSTHESIS, AND TEACHING AND TRAINING FOR SAME	HUANG TA-KO [TW] HUANG JERRY T [TW]	HUANG TA-KO [TW] EPED INC [TW] HUANG TA KO [TW] HUANG JERRY T [TW]	US2015202027A1 US9913701B2	2012-07-23	A61C13/34 A61C13/00 A61C9/00 G09B23/28 A61C5/77 A61C11/00 A61C13/34	A61C13/0004 (EP,US) A61C13/0006 (EP,US) A61C5/77 (US) A61C9/0053 (EP,US) A61C9/006 (EP,US) G09B23/283 (EP,CN,US) A61C11/00 (EP,US) A61C13/34 (EP,US)	2015-07-23 2018-03-13	2014-01-30	049996476

152. AUTOMATIC ROOT-CANAL TREATMENT-MATERIAL ARRANGEMENT AND SUPPLY DEVICE, AND ROOT-CANAL TREATMENT-MATERIAL PACKAGING SYSTEM COMPRISING SAME

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
AUTOMATIC ROOT-CANAL TREATMENT-MATERIAL ARRANGEMENT AND SUPPLY DEVICE, AND ROOT-CANAL TREATMENT-MATERIAL PACKAGING SYSTEM COMPRISING SAME	KIM JAE HWAN [KR]	SPIDENT CO LTD [KR]	US2015113916A1	2012-07-19	A61C19/02 A61C5/04 A61C5/40 A61C5/50 B65B3/14 B65B35/30 B65B35/56	A61C19/00 (KR) A61C19/02 (EP,KR,US) A61C5/40 (EP,US) A61C5/50 (EP,US) B65B19/34 (EP,US) B65B35/30 (KR) B65B35/54 (EP,US) B65B35/56 (EP,KR,US) A61C2202/00 (EP,US)	2015-04-30	2013-08-27	049221303

153. REGENERATION OF AMELOBLAST CELLS AND DENTAL ENAMEL IN VIVO

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
REGENERATION OF AMELOBLAST CELLS AND DENTAL ENAMEL IN VIVO	MOUNIR MAHA MOHAMED FOUAD [EG]	MOUNIR MAHA MOHAMED FOUAD [EG]	US2014023979A1	2012-07-18	A61C19/06 A61C5/04 A61D5/00	A61C19/063 (EP,US) A61C5/50 (EP,US) A61K35/32 (EP,US) A61K38/39 (EP,US) A61K45/06 (EP,US) A61K6/56 (EP,US) A61K6/50, C08L89/00, INV (EP,US) A61K6/56, C08L89/00, INV (EP,US) A61K6/884, C08L89/00, INV (EP,US)	2014-01-23	2014-01-23	049946822

154. COMPOSITIONS FOR ENDODONTIC PROCEDURES

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
COMPOSITIONS FOR ENDODONTIC PROCEDURES	BERGER TODD [US] WILKINSON KEVIN [US] BARANTZ ADAM [US] AMMON DAN [US]	DENTSPLY INT INC [US]	US2014017636A1 US9351909B2	2012-07-13	A61C5/04 A61K6/04 A61K6/838 A61K6/891 A61K6/896 A61K6/00 C08L9/00	A61C5/50 (EP,US) A61K6/54 (EP,US) A61K6/77 (EP,US) A61K6/887 (EP,US) A61K6/896 (EP,US) C07F7/0838 (EP,US) C08F220/325 (EP,US) C08F230/02 (US) C08F230/08 (EP,US) A61K6/54,	2014-01-16 2016-05-31	2014-01-16	048906492

155. ORAL APPLIANCE FOR DELIVERY OF MEDICAMENTS AND/OR OTHER SUBSTANCES									
Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
ORAL APPLIANCE FOR DELIVERY OF MEDICAMENTS AND/OR OTHER SUBSTANCES	ZEGARELLI PETER JOHN [US]	ZEGARELLI PETER JOHN [US]	US2015282913A1 US9649182B2	2012-07-06	A61B10/00 A61B6/51 A61C19/06 A61C9/00 B29C67/00 G05B15/02 G06F17/50 A61B1/24 A61B8/08 A61C3/00 A61K35/38 A61K8/04 A61K9/00 A61K9/06 A61Q11/00 B33Y50/02 G05B19/4099 G06T17/00 G06T19/00 A61C13/00 B29C35/08 B29K105/00 B29L31/00 B33Y10/00 B33Y80/00	A61B1/24 (US) A61B10/0051 (EP,US) A61B6/51 (US) A61B8/0875 (US) A61C13/0013 (EP,US) A61C19/063 (EP,US) A61C19/066 (EP,US) A61C5/90 (EP,US) A61C9/004 (US) A61C9/0053 (US) A61K35/38 (US) A61K8/042 (US) A61K9/0053 (US) A61K9/0063 (US) A61K9/06 (US) A61Q11/00 (US) B29C64/135 (EP,US) B29C64/386 (EP,US) B33Y50/02 (US) G05B15/02 (US) G05B19/4099 (US) G06F30/00 (US) G06T17/00 (US) G06T19/00 (EP,US) H02K1/16 (US) H02K1/2733 (US) H02K1/30 (US) H02K11/215 (US) H02K29/06 (US) H02K29/08 (US) B29C2035/0827 (US) B29C35/0805 (US) B29K2105/0061 (US) B29L2031/753 (US) B33Y10/00 (EP,US) B33Y80/00 (EP,US) G06T2210/41 (EP,US)	2015-10-08 2017-05-16	2014-01-09	049878774
156. DENTAL TOOL COMPRISING A VERSATILE TIP									
Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
DENTAL TOOL COMPRISING A VERSATILE TIP	CHEVALIER ERIC [CH]	NOVENDO SARL [FR]	US2015150647A1	2012-07-03	A61C1/00 A61C19/04 A61C5/42	A61C1/0015 (EP,US) A61C17/18 (EP,US)	2015-06-04	2014-01-09	049170760

						A61C19/04 (US) A61C3/02 (EP,US) A61C5/42 (EP,US) A61C17/20 (EP,US) A61C2204/005 (EP)			
157. Root canal instrument has working area fixed to shaft, where working area in axial direction has three areas which are provided with different twist angles, and working area has cutting edges opposite-lying to each other									
Title Root canal instrument has working area fixed to shaft, where working area in axial direction has three areas which are provided with different twist angles, and working area has cutting edges opposite-lying to each other	Inventors KRUMSIEK MICHAEL [DE] CAKIR OEMER [DE]	Applicants BRASELER GMBH & CO KG GEB [DE]	Publication number DE102012012986A1	Earliest priority 2012-06-29	IPC A61C5/02 A61C5/42	CPC A61C5/42 (EP) B65D83/08 (EP) C03C10/0009 (EP) C03C3/112 (EP)	Publication date 2014-01-02	Earliest publication 2013-03-15	Family number 049323502
158. ENDODONTIC INSTRUMENT FOR DRILLING ROOT CANALS									
Title ENDODONTIC INSTRUMENT FOR DRILLING ROOT CANALS	Inventors BREGUET OLIVIER [CH]	Applicants FKG DENTAIRE S A [CH]	Publication number US2015313686A1 US9724174B2	Earliest priority 2012-06-26	IPC A61C5/02 A61B17/16 A61C5/42	CPC A61B17/1615 (US) A61C5/42 (EP,US)	Publication date 2015-11-05 2017-08-08	Earliest publication 2013-12-31	Family number 047172180
159. GUTTA-PERCHA SEALANT HAVING REMOVABLE ELECTRODE FOR LOCATING APICAL FORAMEN									
Title GUTTA-PERCHA SEALANT HAVING REMOVABLE ELECTRODE FOR LOCATING APICAL FORAMEN	Inventors BECKER ARIK [IL] SAVIN GABRIEL [IL] LEVY HAIM [IL]	Applicants MEDIC NRG LTD [IL]	Publication number WO2013190539A1	Earliest priority 2012-06-19	IPC A61C5/04 A61C5/50 A61C19/04	CPC A61C5/50 (EP) A61C19/042 (EP)	Publication date 2013-12-27	Earliest publication 2013-12-27	Family number 048747649
160. DENTAL FILES TO TREAT MOLAR ROOTCANALS									
Title DENTAL FILES TO TREAT MOLAR ROOTCANALS	Inventors KIM SUNG JIN [KR]	Applicants KIM SUNG JIN [KR]	Publication number KR20130141840A	Earliest priority 2012-06-18	IPC A61C5/02 A61C5/04	CPC A61C5/42 (KR) A61C5/46 (KR)	Publication date 2013-12-27	Earliest publication 2013-12-27	Family number 049985644
161. Cartridge and dispenser									
Title Cartridge and dispenser	Inventors EVERS MARKUS [DE]	Applicants DENTSPLY DETREY GMBH [DE]	Publication number EP2671534A1	Earliest priority 2012-06-06	IPC A61C5/06 A61C5/62 A61C5/64 A61J1/20 B65D83/00	CPC A61C5/62 (EP) A61C5/64 (EP) A61J1/062 (EP) A61M5/24 (EP) A61M5/31558 (EP) B65D83/768 (EP) A61J1/2089 (EP) A61J7/0053 (EP) A61M2005/2407 (EP)	Publication date 2013-12-11	Earliest publication 2013-12-11	Family number 048628602
162. HANDPIECE FOR ENDODONTIC TREATMENT									
Title HANDPIECE FOR ENDODONTIC TREATMENT	Inventors SIMON STÉPHANE [FR]	Applicants ITENA CLINICAL [FR]	Publication number US10022203B2 US2015125812A1	Earliest priority 2012-06-05	IPC A61C5/02 A61C1/00 A61C5/40	CPC A61C1/0084 (US) A61C1/12 (EP,US)	Publication date 2015-05-07 2018-07-17	Earliest publication 2013-12-06	Family number 048577020

					A61C5/42	A61C1/141			
					A61C1/12	(EP,US)			
					A61C1/14	A61C17/02 (EP)			
						A61C5/40			
						(EP,US)			
						A61C5/42			
						(EP,US)			
						A61C2204/002			
						(EP,US)			

163. NOVEL BACTERIOSTATIC AND ANTI-COLLAGENOLYTIC DENTAL MATERIALS THROUGH THE INCORPORATION OF POLYACRYLIC ACID MODIFIED CuQ NANOPARTICLES

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
NOVEL BACTERIOSTATIC AND ANTI-COLLAGENOLYTIC DENTAL MATERIALS THROUGH THE INCORPORATION OF POLYACRYLIC ACID MODIFIED CuQ NANOPARTICLES	RENNE WALTER GEORGE [US]	MUSC FOUND FOR RES DEV [US] UNIV CLEMSON [US]	US2014037705A1 US9034354B2	2012-05-23	A61K33/34 A61K6/00 C01G3/04 A61C5/08 A61K6/083 C01G3/02 C01G3/12	A61K33/34 (EP,US) A61K6/20 (EP,US) A61K6/30 (EP,US) A61K6/70 (EP,US) A61C5/70 (EP,US) A61K6/889 (EP,US) C01G3/02 (US) C01G3/04 (US) C01G3/12 (US) Y10S977/773 (EP,US)	2014-02-06 2015-05-19	2014-02-06	050025695

164. Root canal file for enlargement and cleaning of root canals for maintenance of diseased tooth, has conical dental drill with handle for manual instrumentation, which is attached at shaft of root canal file

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
Root canal file for enlargement and cleaning of root canals for maintenance of diseased tooth, has conical dental drill with handle for manual instrumentation, which is attached at shaft of root canal file	BOECKLE HARALD [DE]	BOECKLE HARALD [DE]	DE102012010022A1	2012-05-22	A61C5/02 A61C5/42	A61C5/42 (EP)	2013-11-28	2013-11-28	049546775

165. Handheld Device for Delivering Photodynamic Therapy

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
Handheld Device for Delivering Photodynamic Therapy	SOUKOS NIKOLAOS S [US] STASHENKO PHILIP P [US]	SOUKOS NIKOLAOS S [US] STASHENKO PHILIP P [US] FORSYTH INST [US]	US2015030989A1	2012-05-16	A61C19/06 A61N5/06	A61C19/06 (EP,US) A61C19/063 (US) A61C5/40 (EP,US) A61N5/0603 (EP,US) A61N5/062 (US) A61N5/0624 (EP,US) A61N2005/0606 (EP,US) A61N2005/063 (EP,US) A61N2005/0644 (EP,US)	2015-01-29	2013-11-21	049584147

166. ENDODONTIC FILE CONTAINER

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
ENDODONTIC FILE CONTAINER	KIM SU GWAN [KR]	UNIV CHOSUN IACF [KR]	KR101373065B1 KR20130127318A	2012-05-14	A61C19/02 A61C5/02	A61C19/02 (KR) A61C5/44 (KR)	2013-11-22 2014-03-11	2013-11-22	049854943

167. INTEGRATED APPARATUS FOR ROOT CANAL TREATMENT

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
INTEGRATED APPARATUS FOR ROOT CANAL TREATMENT			KR200469259Y1	2012-05-11	A61C19/00 A61C5/02	A61C1/08 (KR) A61C5/40 (KR) A61C5/50 (KR)	2013-09-30	2013-09-30	050736285

168. INTEGRATED APPARATUS BUILT IN PC-BASED DENTAL TREATMENT APPARATUS FOR MEASUREMENT AND ENLARGEMENT OF ROOT CANAL SIMULTANEOUSLY

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
INTEGRATED APPARATUS BUILT IN PC-BASED DENTAL TREATMENT APPARATUS FOR MEASUREMENT AND ENLARGEMENT OF ROOT CANAL SIMULTANEOUSLY	NAM TAE KYE [KR]	DENTI INC S [KR]	KR20130126349A	2012-05-11	A61B1/32 A61C19/04 A61C5/02	A61B5/053 (KR) A61B5/1072 (KR) A61C1/0007 (KR) A61C1/06 (KR) A61C1/082 (KR) A61C19/041 (KR) A61C5/42 (KR) A61C5/44 (KR)	2013-11-20	2013-11-20	049854466

169. Measuring needle for working length of root canal

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
Measuring needle for working length of root canal	TAO HU XIAOFEI ZHANG YINGMING YANG MEIYING SHAO LIYANG GUO CHEN WANG HONGMEI ZHOU	UNIV SICHUAN	CN102631252A	2012-05-09	A61C19/04	A61C5/44 (EP)	2012-08-15	2012-08-15	046615942

170. Jaw Powered Electric Generator

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
Jaw Powered Electric Generator	TRUMBULL THOMAS R [US] JOHNSTON TIMOTHY P [US]	TRUMBULL THOMAS R [US] JOHNSTON TIMOTHY P [US] PLANTRONICS [US]	US2013300345A1 US9044291B2	2012-05-09	H02J7/32 F03G5/06 H02N2/18 A61C13/271 A61C5/08 A63B71/08	A61C13/26 (EP,US) A61C5/70 (EP,US) F03G5/06 (US) F03G5/062 (EP) H02N2/18 (EP,US) A63B71/085 (EP,US)	2013-11-14 2015-06-02	2013-11-14	049548125

171. ENDODONTIC FILE MEASURING DEVICE

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
ENDODONTIC FILE MEASURING DEVICE	KIM SU GWAN [KR]	UNIV CHOSUN IACF [KR]	KR101373064B1 KR20130124661A	2012-05-07	A61C19/04 A61C5/02	A61C19/04 (KR) A61C5/44 (KR)	2013-11-15 2014-03-11	2013-11-15	049853356

172. MODIFIED PORCELAIN VENEER FOR BONDING TO BIOCERAMICS

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
MODIFIED PORCELAIN VENEER FOR BONDING TO BIOCERAMICS	PIASCIK JEFFREY ROBERT [US] STONER BRIAN R [US]	RES TRIANGLE INST [US]	US2015079408A1	2012-04-19	A61C13/08 A61C13/083 A61C5/08 A61C5/77 A61C8/00	A61C13/082 (US) A61C13/083 (EP,US) A61C5/20 (EP,US) A61C5/70 (EP,US) A61C5/73 (US)	2015-03-19	2013-10-24	049384056

						A61C5/77 (EP,US) A61C8/005 (US) A61K6/20 (EP,US) A61K6/816 (EP,US) A61K6/818 (EP,US) A61L27/10 (EP,US) A61L27/306 (EP,US) A61L2430/12 (EP,US)			
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173. IRRIGATION DEVICE FOR ROOT CANAL CLEANING

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
IRRIGATION DEVICE FOR ROOT CANAL CLEANING			KR200462769Y1	2012-04-16	A61C17/02 A61C17/20 A61M3/02	A61C1/07 (KR) A61C17/0202 (KR) A61C17/20 (KR) A61C5/40 (KR) A61M3/0204 (KR) A61M3/0275 (KR) A61M2210/0637 (KR)	2012-09-27	2012-09-27	047559990

174. APPARATUS AND METHOD FOR ENDODONTIC TREATMENT

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
APPARATUS AND METHOD FOR ENDODONTIC TREATMENT	LIFSHITZ AMNON [IL] DARSHAN YEHUDA [IL]	FLUIDFILE LTD [IL]	US10327866B2 US2017319292A1	2012-04-15	A61C1/00 A61C17/02 A61C17/022 A61C17/06 A61C3/025 A61C5/40 A61C1/08 A61C1/12	A61C1/0061 (EP) A61C1/0092 (EP,CN,KR,US) A61C1/087 (KR) A61C1/12 (KR) A61C17/02 (CN) A61C17/0202 (EP,CN,KR,US) A61C17/0208 (EP,KR) A61C17/022 (CN,KR,US) A61C17/024 (EP,US) A61C17/08 (CN,KR,US) A61C3/025 (EP,CN,KR,US) A61C5/40 (EP,CN,KR,US) A61C1/0061 (CN,US) A61C1/087 (EP,CN,US) A61C1/12 (EP,US) A61C17/0208 (CN,US) A61C17/022 (EP)	2017-11-09 2019-06-25	2013-10-24	046614921

175. APPARATUS AND METHOD FOR ENDODONTIC TREATMENT

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
APPARATUS AND METHOD FOR ENDODONTIC TREATMENT	LIFSHITZ AMNON [IL] DARSHAN YEHUDA [IL]	SONENDO INC [US]	US2022054230A1	2012-04-15	A61C1/00 A61C17/02 A61C17/022 A61C17/024 A61C17/08 A61C3/025 A61C5/40	A61C1/0092 (US) A61C17/0202 (EP,US) A61C17/0208 (EP) A61C17/022 (US) A61C17/024 (US) A61C17/028 (EP) A61C17/08 (US) A61C3/025 (EP,US) A61C5/40 (EP,US) A61C1/0061 (US) A61C1/087 (US) A61C1/12 (US) A61C17/0208 (US)	2022-02-24	2022-02-24	080269140

176. AN ENDODONTIC FILE

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
AN ENDODONTIC FILE	CHOI EUN CHEOL [KR] CHOI JEONG CHUL [KR] KUM KEE YEON [KR] CHANG SEOK WOO [KR]	GLOBAL TOP INC [KR]	KR20130114888A	2012-04-10	A61C3/02 A61C5/02	A61C5/42 (KR) A61C5/46 (KR)	2013-10-21	2013-10-21	049634692

177. DENTAL SCALER FOR ROOT CANAL TREATMENT AND OTHER PURPOSES

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
DENTAL SCALER FOR ROOT CANAL TREATMENT AND OTHER PURPOSES	PARK BYEONG-HWAL [KR]	PARK BYEONG-HWAL [KR]	WO2013151240A1	2012-04-06	A61C17/18 A61C5/02 A61C5/04 A61C5/42	A61C17/16 (KR) A61C17/18 (EP,US) A61C5/42 (EP,US)	2013-10-10	2013-10-10	049300691

178. METHOD FOR CUTTING OR ABRADING WITH A TOOL, AND RELATED DRIVERS AND SYSTEMS

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
METHOD FOR CUTTING OR ABRADING WITH A TOOL, AND RELATED DRIVERS AND SYSTEMS	SHIPLEY JAMES [US]	ASEPTICO INC [US]	US2015125807A1 US9974627B2	2012-04-06	A61C5/02 A61C1/00 A61C1/18 A61C3/02 A61B17/16 A61C3/00 A61C5/40 A61B17/00 A61B17/32	A61B17/1626 (EP,US) A61C1/0015 (US) A61C1/003 (EP,US) A61C1/186 (EP,US) A61C3/02 (US) A61C5/40 (EP,US) A61B17/32002 (EP,US) A61B2017/00075 (EP,US)	2015-05-07 2018-05-22	2013-10-10	049301107

179. PHOTON INDUCED ACOUSTIC STREAMING DEVICE AND METHOD

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
PHOTON INDUCED ACOUSTIC STREAMING DEVICE AND METHOD	FREGOSO GILBERT [US] HECKERMAN BRAD B [US]	AMERICAN EAGLE INSTR INC [US]	US2015056567A1 US9931187B2	2012-04-05	A61C5/02 A61C17/02 A61C19/06 A61C5/40	A61C17/02 (EP,US) A61C19/06 (US) A61C5/40 (EP,US)	2015-02-26 2018-04-03	2013-10-10	049300893

180. MULTI-FUNCTIONAL MICRO AND NANOPARTICLES FOR USE IN ROOT CANAL THERAPIES

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number

MULTI-FUNCTIONAL MICRO AND NANOPARTICLES FOR USE IN ROOT CANAL THERAPIES	KISHEN ANIL [CA] SHRESTHA ANNIE [CA]	GOVERNING COUNCIL UNIV TORONTO [CA]	US11737955B2 US2018185249A1	2012-03-22	A61C5/40 A61C5/55 A61K41/00 A61K6/00 A61K9/51 A61N5/06 A61K6/17 A61K6/52 A61K6/54 A61K6/62 A61K6/65	A61C5/40 (EP,US) A61C5/55 (EP,US) A61K41/0057 (EP,US) A61K6/17 (EP,US) A61K6/52 (EP,US) A61K6/52 (EP,US) A61K6/54 (EP,US) A61K6/62 (EP,US) A61K6/65 (EP,US) A61K9/5161 (EP,US) A61N5/062 (US) A61P41/00 (EP)	2018-07-05 2023-08-29	2013-09-26	049221751
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181. SUBSTANCES AND METHODS FOR REPLACING NATURAL TOOTH MATERIAL

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
SUBSTANCES AND METHODS FOR REPLACING NATURAL TOOTH MATERIAL	TORABINEJAD MAHMOUD [US] MOADDEL HOMAYOUN [US]	UNIV LOMA LINDA [US]	US2015157538A1	2012-03-21	A61C5/02 A61C5/04 A61K6/06	A61C5/40 (EP,US) A61K6/17 (EP,US) A61K6/54 (EP,US) A61K6/84 (EP,US) A61K6/849 (EP,US) A61K6/851 (EP,US) A61K6/853 (EP,US) C04B14/30 (US) C04B7/02 (US)	2015-06-11	2013-09-26	049223327

182. DENTAL FILLING MACHINE WHICH HEATS FILLING MATERIAL USING INDUCTION

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
DENTAL FILLING MACHINE WHICH HEATS FILLING MATERIAL USING INDUCTION	JUNG DU ROK [KR] SHIN KYOUNG SOO [KR]	DXM CO LTD [KR]	WO2013141564A1	2012-03-20	A61C5/04 A61C5/55 A61M5/14	A61C5/55 (EP) A61M5/145 (KR)	2013-09-26	2012-12-07	047907180

183. A ROOT CANAL FILLER

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
A ROOT CANAL FILLER	JANSE VAN RENSBURG FREDERICK CORNELIUS [ZA]	JANSE VAN RENSBURG FREDERICK CORNELIUS [ZA]	ZA201407461B	2012-03-15	A61C5/50 A61C5/73	A61C5/50 (EP) A61K6/54 (EP)	2015-11-25	2013-09-19	049161894

184. MEDICAL INSTRUMENT MADE OF MONOCRYSTALLINE SHAPE MEMORY ALLOYS AND MANUFACTURING METHODS

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
MEDICAL INSTRUMENT MADE OF MONOCRYSTALLINE SHAPE MEMORY ALLOYS AND MANUFACTURING METHODS	GAO YONG [US] AMMON DAN [US]	GAO YONG [US] AMMON DAN [US] DENTSPLY INT INC [US]	US2013240092A1	2012-03-15	A61C5/02 A61C7/20 B22D25/02 B23P15/00	A61C5/42 (EP,US) A61C7/20 (EP,US) B22D25/02 (EP,US) B23P15/00 (US)	2013-09-19	2013-09-19	048048230

						C22C1/02 (EP,US) C22C14/00 (EP,US) C22C19/007 (EP,US) C22C19/03 (EP,US) C22C38/08 (EP,US) C22C9/01 (EP,US) C22F1/006 (EP,US) C30B15/34 (EP,US) C30B29/52 (EP,US) A61C2201/007 (EP,US) C21D2201/01 (EP,US) C21D2201/04 (EP,US) Y10T29/4998 (EP,US)		
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185. Medical Instrument Made of Monocrystalline Shape Memory Alloys and Manufacturing Methods

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
Medical Instrument Made of Monocrystalline Shape Memory Alloys and Manufacturing Methods	GAO YONG [US] AMMON DAN [US] NDUNGU [US] GEOFFREY KAMAU [US]	GAO YONG [US] AMMON DAN [US] NDUNGU [US] GEOFFREY KAMAU [US] DENTSPLY INT INC [US]	US2018142377A1	2012-03-15	A61C5/42 A61C7/20 C22C1/02 C22C19/03 C22C38/08 C22C9/01 C30B15/34 C30B29/52 C30B33/02 C30B33/10	A61C5/42 (EP,US) A61C7/20 (EP,US) C22C1/02 (EP,US) C22C19/03 (EP,US) C22C38/08 (EP,US) C22C9/01 (EP,US) C30B15/34 (EP,US) C30B29/52 (EP,US) C30B29/66 (EP,US) C30B33/02 (EP,US) C30B33/10 (EP,US) A61C2201/007 (EP,US)	2018-05-24	2018-05-24	062144841

186. ENDODONTIC FILE HOLDER

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
ENDODONTIC FILE HOLDER	LEE IN HWAN [KR]	B & L BIOTECH INC [KR]	KR20130104493A	2012-03-14	A61C19/00 A61C19/04 A61C3/06	A61B90/08 (KR) A61C19/04 (KR) A61C5/42 (KR) A61C5/44 (KR) A61B2090/0803 (KR)	2013-09-25	2013-09-25	049453325

187. APPARATUS AND METHOD FOR ASYMMETRICAL COAST CONTROL OF AN ENDODONTIC MOTOR

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
APPARATUS AND METHOD FOR ASYMMETRICAL COAST CONTROL OF AN ENDODONTIC MOTOR	BROWN ERIK [US] ALOISE CARLOS A [US] SHIPLEY JAMES [US] GAMBARINI GIANLUCA [IT] GLASSMAN GARY [CA] GARMAN GARY T [US]	ORMCO CORP [US]	US2017056129A1 US9895203B2	2012-03-09	A61C1/00 A61C1/06 A61C3/00 A61C5/40 H02P3/06	A61C1/003 (EP,US) A61C1/06 (KR,US) A61C5/40 (EP,US) H02P3/06 (US)	2017-03-02 2018-02-20	2013-09-11	047900695

188. APPARATUS AND METHOD FOR HEATING AN ENDODONTIC INSTRUMENT BY INFRARED RADIATION

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
APPARATUS AND METHOD FOR HEATING AN ENDODONTIC INSTRUMENT BY INFRARED RADIATION	BROWN ERIK [US]	BROWN ERIK [US] ORMCO CORP [US]	US2014030677A1 US9000332B2	2012-03-02	A61C5/04 B29C65/14 F27D1/00	A61C5/55 (EP,US) B29C65/1412 (US)	2014-01-30 2015-04-07	2013-09-05	049043036

189. ROOT CANAL TREATMENT INSTRUMENT

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
ROOT CANAL TREATMENT INSTRUMENT	TAKAHASHI ATSUSHI [JP]	TAKAHASHI ATSUSHI [JP]	WO2013128952A1	2012-02-29	A61C13/15 A61C5/00 A61C5/04	A61C19/004 (EP) A61C5/50 (EP) A46D1/0207 (EP) A61C3/005 (EP)	2013-09-06	2013-09-06	049082162

190. DENTAL IMPLANT ASSEMBLY, IMPLANT, PROSTHESIS TO REPLACE A NONFUNCTIONAL NATURAL TOOTH, INTEGRATED SUPPORT DEVICE FOR PROVIDING TEMPORARY PRIMARY STABILITY TO DENTAL IMPLANTS AND PROSTHESIS, AND RELATED METHODS

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
DENTAL IMPLANT ASSEMBLY, IMPLANT, PROSTHESIS TO REPLACE A NONFUNCTIONAL NATURAL TOOTH, INTEGRATED SUPPORT DEVICE FOR PROVIDING TEMPORARY PRIMARY STABILITY TO DENTAL IMPLANTS AND PROSTHESIS, AND RELATED METHODS	RUBBERT RUEDGER [DE] NESBIT LEA ELLERMEIER [US]	NATURAL DENTAL IMPLANTS AG [DE]	WO2013124260A2 WO2013124260A3	2012-02-23	A61C8/00	A61C13/0001 (EP) A61C13/0004 (EP,US) A61C5/007 (EP,US) A61C8/0009 (EP) A61C8/005 (EP) A61C8/0066 (EP,US) A61C8/0036 (EP) A61C8/0048 (EP) A61C8/008 (EP) G16H20/40 (US)	2013-08-29 2013-10-17	2013-08-29	047882119

191. Dispensing Container for Dental Compound

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
Dispensing Container for Dental Compound	FRITZE JOACHIM [DE]	TRANSCODENT GMBH & CO KG [US] TRANSCODENT GMBH & CO KG [DE]	US2013216975A1	2012-02-22	A61C19/06 A61C5/62	A61C19/063 (US) A61C5/62 (EP,US) A61C5/50 (EP,US) A61M5/349 (EP,US) B05C17/00593 (EP,US)	2013-08-22	2013-08-22	047561451

192. Dispensing Container for Dental Compound

Title	Inventors	Applicants	Publication number	Earliest priority	IPC	CPC	Publication date	Earliest publication	Family number
Dispensing Container for Dental Compound	FRITZE JOACHIM [DE]	TRANSCODENT GMBH & CO KG [DE]	US2015342714A1	2012-02-22	A61C17/02 A61C19/06 A61C5/06	A61C17/0202 (US) A61C19/063 (US) A61C5/62 (EP,US) A61C5/50	2015-12-03	2015-12-03	054700465

						(EP,US) A61M5/349 (EP,US) B05C17/00593 (EP,US)			
193. VIRTUALLY DESIGNING A POST AND CORE RESTORATION USING A DIGITAL 3D SHAPE									
Title VIRTUALLY DESIGNING A POST AND CORE RESTORATION USING A DIGITAL 3D SHAPE	Inventors FISKER RUNE [DK] NONBOE SVEN [DK]	Applicants 3SHAPE AS [US] 3SHAPE AS [DK]	Publication number US2013209965A1 US8974229B2	Earliest priority 2012-02-10	IPC A61C13/00 A61C5/08 A61C5/70 A61C13/30 A61C9/00	CPC A61C13/30 (EP,US) A61C19/04 (US) A61C5/70 (EP,US) A61C9/0046 (EP,US) G16H20/40 (US)	Publication date 2013-08-15 2015-03-10	Earliest publication 2013-08-10	Family number 047631373
194. Reamer with an improved blade for root canal preparation									
Title Reamer with an improved blade for root canal preparation	Inventors MALAGNINO VITO ANTONIO [IT]	Applicants MALAGNINO VITO ANTONIO [IT] SWEDEN & MARTINA SPA [IT]	Publication number US2014356809A1 US9408674B2	Earliest priority 2012-01-30	IPC A61C5/02 A61C5/42	CPC A61C5/42 (EP,US)	Publication date 2014-12-04 2016-08-09	Earliest publication 2013-08-08	Family number 045809345
195. CONDENSER FOR ROOT CANAL TREATMENT									
Title CONDENSER FOR ROOT CANAL TREATMENT	Inventors RYU HYEON SEOCK [KR]	Applicants DENTI INC S [KR]	Publication number KR20130086845A	Earliest priority 2012-01-26	IPC A61C5/04 A61M5/142	CPC A61C3/08 (KR) A61C5/55 (KR) A61C5/62 (KR) A61C2204/002 (KR)	Publication date 2013-08-05	Earliest publication 2013-08-05	Family number 049213917
196. ROOT CANAL FILLING APPARATUS DETACHABLE PLUNGER									
Title ROOT CANAL FILLING APPARATUS DETACHABLE PLUNGER	Inventors RYU HYEON SEOCK [KR]	Applicants DENTI INC S [KR]	Publication number KR101261408B1	Earliest priority 2012-01-26	IPC A61C3/08 A61C5/04 A61M5/14	CPC A61C3/08 (KR) A61C5/55 (KR) A61C5/62 (KR)	Publication date 2013-05-10	Earliest publication 2013-05-10	Family number 048665609
197. Multi-Planar Pre-Curved Rotary Endodontic File									
Title Multi-Planar Pre-Curved Rotary Endodontic File	Inventors JOHNSON WILLIAM B [US]	Applicants JOHNSON WILLIAM B [US]	Publication number US2013189644A1 US9078722B2	Earliest priority 2012-01-20	IPC A61C5/02	CPC A61C5/42 (EP,US)	Publication date 2013-07-25 2015-07-14	Earliest publication 2013-07-25	Family number 047747766
198. DENTAL HANDPIECE CONTROL APPARATUS									
Title DENTAL HANDPIECE CONTROL APPARATUS	Inventors KUNISADA MAKOTO [JP]	Applicants NAKANISHI INC [JP]	Publication number US2014322669A1 US9827069B2	Earliest priority 2012-01-16	IPC A61C5/02 A61C1/00 A61C1/18 A61C19/04 A61C5/40	CPC A61C1/003 (EP,KR,US) A61C1/06 (KR) A61C1/186 (EP,KR,US) A61C19/042 (EP,KR,US) A61C5/40 (EP,US) A61C5/42 (US) F04C2270/0421 (EP,US)	Publication date 2014-10-30 2017-11-28	Earliest publication 2013-07-25	Family number 048799036
199. DENTAL WEDGE									
Title DENTAL WEDGE	Inventors ERKSINE-SMITH CRAIG MATHEW [AU] ERSKINE-	Applicants ERKSINE PRODUCTS PTY LTD [AU]	Publication number US10299890B2 US2016361138A1	Earliest priority 2012-01-13	IPC A61C5/12 A61C3/10	CPC A61C3/10 (EP,US)	Publication date 2016-12-15 2019-05-28	Earliest publication 2013-07-18	Family number 048780967

	SMITH CRAIG MATHEW [AU]	ERSKINE PRODUCTS PTY LTD [AU]			A61C5/88 A61C7/00	A61C5/88 (EP,US)			
200. System and Method for Performing Endodontic Procedures with Lasers									
Title System and Method for Performing Endodontic Procedures with Lasers	Inventors OSTLER CALVIN D [US]	Applicants OSTLER CALVIN D [US] DENTSPLY INT INC [US]	Publication number US2013177865A1	Earliest priority 2012-01-06	IPC A61C1/00 A61C5/02 A61C5/04	CPC A61C1/0046 (EP,US) A61C5/40 (EP,US) A61C5/50 (EP,US) H01S3/2391 (EP,US) H01S3/005 (EP,US) H01S3/0071 (EP,US) H01S3/0092 (EP,US) H01S3/1605 (EP,US) H01S3/1611 (EP,US) H01S3/1643 (EP,US)	Publication date 2013-07-11	Earliest publication 2013-07-11	Family number 047631709
201. POLYMERIC INSTRUMENT FOR CLEANING CANALS IN ENDODONTIC PROCEDURES									
Title POLYMERIC INSTRUMENT FOR CLEANING CANALS IN ENDODONTIC PROCEDURES	Inventors MCCAFFERTY RYAN J [US] QUIGLEY MICHAEL [US]	Applicants MCCAFFERTY RYAN J [US] QUIGLEY MICHAEL [US] SS WHITE BURS INC [US]	Publication number US2013171581A1 US9226802B2	Earliest priority 2012-01-02	IPC A61C19/04 A61C5/02	CPC A61C19/041 (EP,US) A61C5/42 (EP,US) A61C5/44 (EP,US)	Publication date 2013-07-04 2016-01-05	Earliest publication 2013-07-04	Family number 048695069